

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

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Report with new business models for sustainable craft

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About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the regional craft ecosystems of Bassano del Grappa (IT), Bornholm (DK), Dals Långed (SE), and Venice (IT), the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable. HEPHAESTUS will test and evaluate solutions co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a "Future of Craft" Green Living Lab situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a sustainable network (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project's results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long-lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

Objective 1: Develop new sustainable business models for the craft sectors.

Objective 2: Combine cutting-edge technologies with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.

Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of craft in the future, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.

Objective 4: Develop a lifelong learning methodology and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.

Objective 5: Establish a Green Living Lab for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.

Objective 6: To design and operationalise a bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. A unique value-added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

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1.0 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of Task 1.3 of the HEPHAESTUS project, focusing on the development of new sustainable business models for the craft sector. Working across the project's regional craft ecosystems in Venice, Bornholm, Dals Långed (and Fengersfors), and Bassano del Grappa (and Nove), the report examines how craft-based enterprises and practices create, communicate and sustain value under contemporary conditions of social, cultural, environmental and economic transformation. Craft business models are approached as configurations in which economic viability is intertwined with cultural continuity, ecological responsibility, local embeddedness, education, material experimentation and social relation.

The report combines literature-based analysis with empirical case studies and participatory educational activities. It uses the Business Model Canvas (BMC) selectively as an initial vocabulary through which the specific tensions of craft business can be made visible. Across the cases, the analysis shows that craft businesses often depend on forms of value that extend beyond conventional categories of revenue, customer segments, and channels. These include place-based authenticity, shared experience, tacit knowledge, responsible material use, collective infrastructures, and the capacity to shape how customers and publics come to value craft. On the basis of these findings, the report has generated a toolkit for sustainable craft business model reflection (Appendix C). The toolkit translates the report's analytical insights into a set of practical prisms, questions and points of orientation that craft makers can use to reflect on their own practices, identify tensions, and explore possible directions for future development.

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2.0 Purpose and Structure of the Report

The purpose of this report is to develop an empirically grounded and analytically informed understanding of sustainable business models for craft within the HEPHAESTUS project. In line with WP1 and Task 1.3, the report examines how craft makers, workshops, collective initiatives and craft-related institutions create and sustain value across the project's regional ecosystems. Attention is given to the ways in which economic viability is connected to cultural heritage, ecological responsibility, local embeddedness, education, material experimentation and social relation. The report also provides the analytical foundation for the toolkit developed as an outcome of this deliverable (Appendix C). The toolkit translates the report's findings into reflective prisms, guiding questions and practical prompts that can support craft makers and related stakeholders in examining their own business models and identifying possible directions for sustainable development.

The report is structured as follows. It first presents the methodology and the empirical basis of the work, including fieldwork, student engagement, qualitative case research and collaboration with craft makers and project partners. It then introduces the BOFA Challenge as a project-based exploration of circular economy and craft-based business model innovation in Bornholm. The following section develops the literature review and analytical framework, including the selective use of the Business Model Canvas and the report's central analytical categories. The main body of the report presents case analyses from Venice, Bornholm, Dals Långed and Fengersfors, and Bassano del Grappa and Nove. The final analytical section draws together the recurring findings through a set of prisms in relation to the Business Model Canvas, which also form the basis of the toolkit for sustainable craft business model reflection.

3.0 Methodology

This Deliverable 1.3 is based on empirical fieldwork, educational engagement, and participatory methods conducted across the multiple HEPHAESTUS craft ecosystems throughout the project period. The methodological approach combines practice-based inquiry with structured analytical tools in order to investigate emerging business models and value creation processes within contemporary craft.

A core component of the empirical work was carried out through an educational field-work format involving students from the master's programme in Business Administration and Philosophy at Copenhagen Business School. As part of their coursework, several cohorts of students have conducted fieldwork trips to selected ecosystems (Venice in 2022, 2023; Bassano del Grappa in 2024, and Bornholm in 2025), where they engaged closely with individual craft-makers or organized craft-based business practices. This format enabled the collection of situated, practice-based insights while fostering an interactive exchange between academic analysis and real-world contexts. Given the limited scope of this report, three cases were selected within each ecosystem (Bornholm, Venice, Bassano del Grappa) and one extended case from Dals Långed. These cases were chosen strategically, as they highlight tensions that are both recurrent and significant across contexts, particularly in relation to sustainability, technological integration, and business model development. The fieldwork was conducted as a collective research process involving both researchers and students, who participated together in the empirical engagement across the different ecosystems. While individual student groups worked closely with particular craft-makers or craft-based business practices, the research was developed through a shared fieldwork process in which researchers were directly involved in the encounters, maintained dialogue with the craft-makers concerning their business operations, and contributed to the production and analysis of the material. Moreover, this work directly relates to Task 6.2, *Creation and Diffusion of Craft Histories*. Some of the results are also made visible through craft history videos and storytelling materials displayed on the [HEPHAESTUS website](#).

In addition to the student-led fieldwork, targeted qualitative research was conducted in Bornholm by Margot Bustamante, a research assistant of HEPHAESTUS employed at CBS, over a one-month period in 2024. This fieldwork focused on collaboration with the craft-maker Christina Schou and examined her business model, particularly the integration of a crushing machine into her production process. This case provided an in-depth perspective on how technological innovation is incorporated into craft practices and how it reshapes production, value creation, and organisational choices.

Further empirical material was generated through the problem-and solution-oriented approach developed in the course “[The Art of Innovation](#)” in which students were presented with a real-world challenge provided by BOFA. Participants were tasked with developing solutions through business model innovation, thereby exploring how craft-based approaches can address sustainability challenges and resource management issues. This component functioned as an experimental setting for generating and testing new ideas and conceptual approaches to business model development.

The theoretical (and analytical) framework of the study is informed by the application of the Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder &, Pigneur, 2010; Teece, 2010). This tool was used to structure and compare the different cases, enabling a systematic examination of value propositions, value creation processes, stakeholder configurations, and sustainability considerations across craft-based enterprises.

In addition, the development of the Intellectual Property (IP) booklet (Appendix A) relied on data collected in collaboration with Task 4.1 and 4.2 (WP4), complemented by a survey targeting craft-makers. This ensures that the content of the booklet is aligned with the needs, challenges, and practices of the craft community, and that it reflects user-driven insights.

Finally, selected insights and proposed business models will be further tested and refined through engagement with practitioners at the annual HEPHAESTUS Symposium in Bassano del Grappa in April 2026. This upcoming stage introduces an element of validation and iteration, allowing the research findings to be confronted with broader stakeholder perspectives and real-world applicability.

4.0 BOFA Challenge

Directly related to Task 1.3 and the activities of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (WP5) is BOFA's involvement and partnership with Copenhagen Business School. More specifically, this collaboration included co-creation activities with students from the MSc in Organisational Innovation and Entrepreneurship, enrolled in the course Art of Innovation. In collaboration with BOFA, Bornholm's waste management organization, the students explored how circular economy principles could be translated into viable business models within the arts and crafts sector (see Figure 1). The student projects were structured around three research questions (the students chose one of them), each addressing a different dimension of Bornholm's sustainability transition. These included: (1) how public sector organizations such as BOFA can foster circular business models through the recycling of sanitation and waste materials; (2) how slow tourism initiatives can position circular crafts as drivers of cultural tourism and socio-economic resilience; and (3) how Bornholm can move towards becoming a truly zero-waste island. Across the student projects, a shared ambition had emerged. That is, to position Bornholm as a frontrunner in circular economy practices and as a destination in which sustainable craft and tourism mutually reinforce one another. This ambition aligns with the island's broader vision of becoming a zero-waste society by 2032 and a year-round, high-quality tourism destination.

The projects (five are chosen due to the limited scope of this report and are attached as Appendix B) (see Figure 2, 3) collectively explore how circular craftsmanship, enabled by actors such as BOFA, local artisans, and innovation platforms, can form inspiration for new business models that extend beyond traditional production and consumption (Teece, 2010).

They emphasize instead experience-based, collaborative, and place-based value creation, particularly through the lens of sustainable and slow tourism.

The projects took the form of PowerPoint presentations. Each group had 10 minutes to pitch their ideas in front of the class (Figure 1), and received feedback from the BOFA team about applicability, speculative perspectives, and economic feasibility.

Figure 1 - Students presenting their ideas for the "BOFA Challenge" at Copenhagen Business School. Author's own photograph taken 2025

Below is a summary of the various themes that emerged throughout the projects.

Across the student projects, a consistent emphasis is placed on circular craft as the foundation for new business models. Rather than treating waste as a residual output, the projects reframe it as a valuable input for creative production and innovation. In several cases, discarded sanitation materials such as toilets, sinks, and tiles are repurposed into functional and aesthetic objects, including public infrastructure and artistic installations. This reflects core principles of circular economy, where value is maintained through reuse, regeneration, and extended material lifecycles (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). At the level of business models, this shift can be understood as a reconfiguration of value creation, where materials previously considered waste are reintegrated into production processes and contribute to both economic and symbolic value (Bocken et al., 2016).

Figure 2- Example from a students' BOFA Challenge presentation; Source Appendix B

At the same time, the projects consistently integrate these circular practices into tourism-oriented models, particularly within the framework of slow tourism. A recurring challenge identified by the students is the strong seasonality of tourism on Bornholm, which limits economic stability and concentrates environmental pressure during peak periods. In response, many proposals aim to extend visitor engagement beyond the summer season by offering immersive and longer-term experiences. This aligns with the concept of the experience economy, where value is generated through staged, meaningful interactions rather than the mere exchange of goods (Pine & Gilmore, 2013; 1999). In this context, circular craft becomes embedded within tourism experiences, enabling new forms of value creation that combine environmental sustainability with cultural engagement.

Figure 3 - Example from students' BOFA Challenge presentation; Source Appendix B

Another key pattern is the shift towards participatory and experience-based value creation. Visitors are not positioned as passive consumers but are actively involved in workshops, co-creation processes, and learning activities. For instance, concepts such as workshop-based tourism and “circularity passports” incentivize repeated engagement and transform the tourist experience into an ongoing relationship with the destination. This reflects a move towards co-creation logics, where value emerges through interactions between providers and users rather than being delivered unilaterally (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). From a business model perspective, this implies a shift in the value proposition from products to experiences, and in value capture from one-time transactions to longer-term engagement.

The role of BOFA and other public sector actors is consistently framed as enabling and not directive. Across the projects, BOFA is positioned as a central facilitator that provides access to materials, supports logistics, and creates the conditions for collaboration between stakeholders. In some proposals, this role is further expanded through the development of institutional structures, such as innovation hubs (e.g. The HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab), which aim to centralize knowledge exchange and foster entrepreneurship. This reflects an ecosystem perspective on business models, where value creation depends on the coordination of multiple actors across sectors (Adner, 2017). Public sector organizations

play a key role in orchestrating these ecosystems by reducing fragmentation and enabling resource flows.

Collaboration emerges as a critical component of all proposed business models. The projects highlight the need to integrate a wide range of actors, including local artisans, tourism providers, research institutions, and public organizations. Through these partnerships, circular craft is embedded within broader value networks that extend beyond individual firms. This aligns with the growing recognition that sustainable business models are often network-based and rely on interdependent relationships rather than isolated activities (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013). Such configurations increase the potential for innovation, scalability, and resilience.

Finally, the projects collectively address broader structural challenges facing Bornholm, including tourism seasonality, fragmented innovation efforts, and the need for a stronger, unified identity. Several proposals emphasize storytelling and branding strategies that highlight the transformation of waste into craft, thereby strengthening the cultural and symbolic value of circular practices. At the same time, initiatives such as centralized innovation platforms seek to overcome fragmentation by creating shared spaces for collaboration and knowledge exchange. These approaches point towards more integrated business models in which environmental, cultural, and economic dimensions are closely interconnected, supporting long-term socio-economic sustainability on the island.

5.0 Business Models for Craft: Literature Review and Analytical Framework

5.1 Challenges and avenues in relation to craft business models

Besides what has been identified within the HEPHAESTUS project, several business model-related challenges relevant to craft have also been reported both in European contexts and beyond. Within the European context, Rauhut et al. (2020) emphasize pressures associated with digital transformation, alongside limited capacity to respond in small craft firms, including constraints in skills, competencies and resources, as well as broader pressures associated with dynamic market conditions, including shortages of skilled labor and increasing competition from enterprises outside the craft sector. Kofler and Walder (2024) point to rising input costs and continued exposure to wider market developments despite local embeddedness, suggesting that the craft sector may be locally grounded while still dependent on developments such as energy and material costs. The European Crafts Alliance and Ohayō (2025) similarly argue that the increasing hybridization of the craft ecosystem complicates classification and institutional support, since craft often spans cultural, artistic, industrial, commercial and tourism-related spheres, which they describe as “a true administrative puzzle” (European Crafts Alliance and Ohayō, 2025, p. 3). Their wider

reporting further suggests that the absence of official statistics and sector-specific data weakens the basis for tailored policy support, while craftspeople and sector experts across Europe identify competition, lack of entrepreneurial skills, high production costs, decreasing purchasing power and rigid tax systems as recurrent challenges (European Crafts Alliance & Ohayō, 2025). Recent research by Cappellieri et al. (2022) on the future of the crafts sector also indicates that digitalization is not simply a technical matter, as it may open possibilities for efficiency, transparency and new forms of work, but that these possibilities are often experienced by smaller enterprises as costly and demanding in terms of time, money and competences (see also OECD, 2021). Finally, Rauhut et al. (2020) also note that business model innovation (BMI) methods are often perceived as too complex, and that craft owners may have limited awareness of BMI's relevance or may find it difficult to identify suitable business model approaches.

Additional business model-related challenges concerning craft have also been reported in non-European contexts. Majumdar and Banerjee (2017) emphasize structural and socio-cultural constraints affecting micro-scale craft enterprises, including weak access to markets, limited managerial capability, lack of online presence, and broader pressures linked to liberalization, subsidy withdrawal, changing gender and generational relations, urban migration and cultural change. In their case material, the absence of online presence is especially marked, and artisans are described as lacking awareness of channels (such as Etsy and Pinterest) through which they might otherwise reach wider markets (Majumdar & Banerjee, 2017). Brown (2019) likewise examines market-access models that promote artisanship to Western markets with minimal intervention, suggesting that sustainable development in the craft sector needs to be evaluated not only in terms of the number of artisans reached, but also in relation to the retention of traditional craft and material culture. Brown's (2019) analysis also warns against supporting products without an end market in view. Finally, studies of maker and creative micro-enterprises conducted by Luckman (2018) and Friedman et al. (2025) highlight channel-related pressures, including visibility problems and the continuing burden of marketing and business logistics as part of sustaining sales activity. Luckman further shows that online craft micro-enterprise involves extensive spatial and temporal negotiations and is often sustained in spite of significant economic trade-offs, while Friedman et al. find that many makers are makers first and entrepreneurs second, that they learn business skills as they go, and that they are often motivated by non-monetary values (Luckman, 2015; Friedman et al., 2025).

As with European research, this broader set of studies offers suggestions for how business models for craft might be enabled and developed, though with a somewhat stronger emphasis on structural conditions. Majumdar and Banerjee (2017) argue for strengthening business capability beyond technical production. Their analysis also implies that business development cannot be separated from the broader socio-cultural and environmental conditions shaping artisan communities (Majumdar & Banerjee, 2017). Brown (2019) points toward the importance of support structures that extend beyond simple market placement. Her typology of market access, new skills and design partnerships also suggests that interventions differ substantially in type and intensity, and that long-term support for traditional craftsmanship matters as much as short-term sales (Brown, 2019). Finally, the work on maker and creative micro-enterprises (Luckman, 2018; Friedman et al., 2025) points to the practical importance of building competence in channel strategy, direct

marketing and the routine work of business logistics required to sustain micro-enterprise sales activity in competitive environments. Friedman et al. (2025) also argue that tools, training and mentorship need to take seriously the “intangibles” that conventional sales and accounting platforms overlook, including creative expression, community engagement, sustainability and value alignment.

Some of these challenges may be less directly applicable to a European context, particularly the serious lack of awareness of digital sales channels, the more acute forms of market disconnection, as well as the specific pressures linked to subsidy withdrawal and rapid urban migration. Others, however, remain clearly relevant across contexts, including limited business capability beyond technical production, uncertainty about viable markets and end users, and the continuing burden of visibility, marketing and business logistics in small-scale craft enterprise. Likewise, some proposed avenues may be less transferable where they presuppose more basic forms of market insertion or markedly different institutional conditions, whereas others remain pertinent, including stronger business capability beyond technical skill, support structures that extend beyond mere market access, and greater attention to the non-monetary values and practical business work that sustain craft micro-enterprise.

Taken together, these cross-context differences do not diminish the relevance of the broader literature for craft, but they do suggest that its challenges and proposed avenues need to be filtered through the specific institutional and socio-economic conditions of the European craft sector. The overall challenges identified in this research, namely digital pressure, limited capacity, cost exposure and unclear institutional fit, as well as the suggestions advanced in response, including business training, mentoring and networking, simpler methods, and forms of traceability and authenticity, are relevant for developing business models for craft. At the same time, the broader literature suggests that these tensions are not only internal firm problems. They are also shaped by the surrounding ecosystem of training, public support, digital infrastructure, intermediary organizations and the wider coordination between craft, heritage, tourism and regional development (OECD, 2021; European Crafts Alliance and Ohayō, 2025).

5.2 From identified challenges to the question of value in craft business

The case-based investigations presented below in relation to the ecosystem of HEPHAESTUS relate to several of the same issues, but they also point toward a further problem. More specifically, they suggest that the question is not only how craft enterprises can strengthen their business capacities within existing business model frameworks, but also whether those frameworks adequately register the kinds of value at stake in craft practice. In turn, this raises the question of whether business model frameworks, as they have been developed theoretically and practically over the last decades, are in fact able to describe craft business adequately – that is, what such a business consists in – and thus whether they are also able to provide relevant prescriptive measures or guidance – that is, how such a business is expected to behave.

Revenue-centered tendencies in mainstream business-model literature

This concern resonates with research that has questioned dominant business model frameworks for their functionalist assumptions, static and linear tendencies and difficulty accounting for hybrid forms of value creation (Doganova & Eyquem-Renault, 2009; Gudiksen, 2015; Spieth et al., 2019). In a widely cited formulation, Teece (2010) argues that a business model “describes the design or architecture of the value creation, delivery, and capture mechanisms” a firm employs, and that its essence lies in defining how the enterprise “delivers value to customers, entices customers to pay for value, and converts those payments to profit” (Teece, 2010, p. 172). In a related vein, Baden-Fuller and Mangematin (2013) stress value capture and monetization through the relation between internal arrangements and external engagement, while Amit and Zott (2001) include the structure of the offering and the information and resource flows needed to sustain the business. A similar emphasis is also evident in accounts that treat business model thinking as a way of organizing distribution and channels, primarily in order to reach new markets and compete within them (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Magretta, 2002;). While such accounts do not reduce business models to profit alone, they do tend to organize the model around economic value capture as their most central reference point.

Opening beyond economic value alone

A more direct response to this revenue-centred tendency is found in Gasparin et al. (2021), who develop a business model for social innovation and relate it to craft making in a broader context. Examining SMEs that work with craft communities and heritage practices, where cultural preservation is pursued through forms of making, skills transmission and locally grounded production, they propose a business model for social innovation, defined as an SME-oriented model designed to sustain the long-term growth of social innovation by specifying mechanisms through which economic as well as social, cultural and ecological value are created and captured. They position this model as an alternative to business model accounts that are largely agnostic about the sources of social, ecological and cultural value, and that tend to focus primarily on the architecture of revenues, costs and profits associated with the delivery of economic value. On their account, SMEs practicing social innovation require a business model able to accommodate two interdependent architectures and activity systems at once: one oriented toward business performance, and one oriented toward societal, cultural and environmental goals. These two systems are analytically distinguishable, but the value proposition of the business only exists through their combination. Related craft research points in a similar direction. Recent work (Panneels, 2023; Newisar et al., 2024) on place-based sustainable enterprise in the craft industry proposes a quintuple bottom line of purpose, profit, people, planet, and place. Related research on heritage-inspired arts and crafts points in a similar direction, showing that craft activity may combine cultural identity, economic development, and community empowerment.

(1) a SOCIALLY FORMATIVE DIMENSION in craft business

The relevance of Gasparin et al. (2021) for the present inquiry is twofold. First, we do not treat craft business as identical with social innovation in any strong or exhaustive sense. Rather, we take their argument to open the possibility that craft business may very often involve a **SOCIALLY FORMATIVE DIMENSION**, insofar as it may pursue broader social, cultural, ecological or place-based aims through economic activity. As we will show in the cases below, this includes, for example, the reactivation of heritage, the transmission of skills, the maintenance or reworking of place-based knowledge, the making of social space, and the cultivation of slowness, attention and continuity against industrial speed and standardization. This reading is also supported by recent maker-entrepreneurship research, demonstrating that many makers value creative expression, sustainability, alternative ways of organizing work, and relationships with customers and communities, and that conventional small-business tools often fail to register such values (Friedman et al., 2025; Luckman, 2015).

(2) a MULTI-VALUE UNDERSTANDING of the business model

Second, we take from Gasparin et al. (2021) the opening toward a **MULTI-VALUE UNDERSTANDING** of the business model. If such concerns are integral to many craft businesses, then business models for craft cannot be centered on economic value and earning potential alone, but must be able to register a plurality of values, some monetized, some only partly monetized, and some pursued precisely because they are not exhausted by market price. Gasparin et al. (2021) are useful here not because they provide a ready-made business model for craft, but because they offer a conceptual lever for moving beyond revenue-centered business model thinking while remaining within a business model framework.

Importantly, Gasparin et al. (2021) do not theorize value in any general sense, but they do make explicit that the business model must register more than economic value alone. While they foreground several domains of value, namely economic, social, cultural and ecological value (see also Quinn, 2022), which they treat as inherent to the activity rather than supplementary to it, they do not develop further distinctions found in the value theories and classifications (see survey by Pauls, 1990). They do not, for example, engage the distinction between object value and value-as-criterion, that is, between the value assigned to an object or phenomenon and the standards in terms of which such an evaluation is made (Brown, 1984; Williams, 1968). Nor do they specify whether their own account is operating at the level of a descriptive, normative or meta-normative theory of value (Dunn, 1983; Gewirth, 1985). Read against those frameworks, Gasparin et al. (2021) can therefore be placed not at the level of a general or meta-theoretical clarification of value, but at the level of a descriptive and classificatory account. More specifically, their differentiation of economic, social, cultural and ecological value comes closest to the kind of complex value typology described by Rescher (1969), where values are distinguished according to such principles as the nature of the benefit, the purposes at issue, or the broader domain in which value appears, yielding categories such as economic, political, aesthetic or spiritual value, and more specific forms such as exchange or truth value. More loosely, Gasparin et al. may also be read alongside Perry's broader mapping of realms of value, where value is distributed

across spheres such as morality, the arts, science, religion, economics and politics (Perry, 1954).

What follows from this for the present inquiry is thus not a general theory of value, but a more limited and workable clarification. The categories suggested by Gasparin et al. (2021) can be treated as a differentiation of value domains within the business model itself. This allows the present inquiry to take economic, social, cultural and ecological value as analytically distinct yet co-present dimensions of craft business, while leaving open the broader theoretical questions concerning the nature and status of value. In that sense, the work of Gasparin et al. (2021) is useful here because it helps open business model analysis toward a plurality of values beyond the economic one alone. We call this a multi-value approach to craft business models.

5.3 The selective and reflective use of the Business Model Canvas

Below we present a series of case studies for which some of the challenges described above are relevant (e.g. digitalization pressures, limited business capability, market visibility challenges, and cost exposure), and in which some of the avenues identified above are also pursued (e.g. business training and mentoring, networking and collaboration, and attention to non-monetary values). Our analytical approach, however, differs from the studies discussed above. Despite the critique that business model thinking has received in relation to craft, and despite the critique directed specifically at the Business Model Canvas (BMC) from several different angles, we nevertheless employ the latter for the purpose of analyzing our case studies and identifying some of the business model-related tensions, challenges and possibilities that craft makers and craft businesses currently meet. Those critiques are not uniform, but they repeatedly converge on the point that the standard BMC does not adequately capture social mission, non-targeted stakeholders, symbolic value or environmental and social layers of value creation (Joyce & Paquin, 2016; Sparviero, 2019; Carter & Carter, 2020).

Adapted from 'Business Model Generation', Alexander Osterwalder, Wiley 2012.
www.businessmodelgeneration.com
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Figure 4 - Business Model Canvas, Retrieved from: Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2013). Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers. John Wiley & Sons.

The standard Business Model Canvas and its nine building blocks.

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) (see Figure 4), introduced by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur (2010), is a one-page framework for describing how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value. In its standard form, it consists of nine building blocks that together provide a shared descriptive vocabulary for discussing a business model. The point of the canvas is not to give a complete theory of business, but to offer a structured overview of the main elements through which a business is organized. They are called building blocks:

- ★ CUSTOMER SEGMENTS. The different groups of people or organizations a business seeks to reach and serve.
- ★ VALUE PROPOSITIONS. The bundle of products and/or services through which the business creates value for a given customer segment.
- ★ CHANNELS. The means through which the business communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver a value proposition.
- ★ CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS, The kinds of relationships the business establishes and maintains with its customer segments.
- ★ REVENUE STREAMS. The ways in which the business generates income from each customer segment.
- ★ KEY RESOURCES. The most important assets required to make the business model work.

- ★ **KEY ACTIVITIES.** The most important things the business must do in order to operate successfully and deliver its value proposition.
- ★ **KEY PARTNERSHIPS.** The network of suppliers, collaborators, and other partners that help the business model function.
- ★ **COST STRUCTURE.** The main costs incurred in operating the business model.

Taken together, the nine building blocks describe four broader dimensions of a business model: customers, offer, infrastructure and financial viability. In this sense, the canvas should help to make visible not only what a business offers and to whom, but also the organizational means and financial conditions through which that offer is sustained.

How the present report uses these categories:

In the analyses that follow, these standard categories {now marked with CAPS in italics} are not used as a complete or exhaustive scheme. They are used selectively and reflectively, as a first descriptive vocabulary for identifying what a given craft practice proposes as valuable, to whom that value is directed, through which means it is sustained, and where tensions arise when these elements do not fit smoothly together.

This means that we do not adopt the BMC uncritically, neither as a complete description of craft business, nor as a means to prescribe what they should do to do business. Rather, we use it as an analytical instrument and, more specifically, as an INITIAL DESCRIPTIVE VOCABULARY for identifying areas of tension. Just as with the set of cases we have chosen from the different HEPHAESTUS ecosystems, not all of the challenges discussed above apply equally to all cases of making a business with craft. Yet our aim is to describe a spectrum of tensions and matters to note productively that may offer something to many craft makers in comparable situations – not as a general scheme, and not as a new business model canvas, but rather as a selection of possible productive insights that may indicate ways forward while also helping to identify what may prove troublesome.

On the one hand, we therefore retain the BMC because it provides a set of relatively well-established categories for describing the basic building blocks of businesses and business models. Craft makers in the project are already familiar with these categories, or have been introduced to them in the previous workshops (e.g. co-creation workshop in Bornholm 2024), some have used them directly, and most are comparatively easy to understand. In that sense, the BMC offers a shared descriptive vocabulary. This is especially useful in a field where businesses frequently combine fairs, design shops, online platforms, workshops and experience-based activities rather than relying on one stable route to market (Luckman, 2015; European Crafts Alliance & Ohayō, 2025).

5.4 The relation between CRAFT VALUE PROPOSITION and HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER

On the other hand, we retain it because, at a higher level of abstraction, it allows us to identify and articulate what appear to be two especially fundamental categories for the present inquiry. First, we point to the craft value proposition, normally understood as the

bundle of products and services that create value for a specific customer segment (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010), but understood here more broadly as the set of values that the craft business proposes by virtue of its products, services, experiences and existence. We call this the CRAFT VALUE PROPOSITION. Second, there is the craft customer segment, normally understood as the different groups of people or organizations an enterprise aims to reach and serve (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010), but understood here as the particular kind of buyer, person, public or audience for whom that proposed value is expected or hoped to resonate. We call this THE HOPED-FOR CRAFT CUSTOMER.

By proceeding in this way, we work on the assumption that each business presents a specific relation between a value proposition and a hoped-for customer segment, and that this relation expresses something fundamental about the business as a business: as something that seeks to do something in the world, and with the world. At the same time, we also assume that craft businesses display recurring features in this respect that can be identified and articulated across cases. This is relevant not least because recent European market research suggests that hoped-for responsiveness in craft markets often depends not only on price or utility, but also on traditional production techniques, uniqueness, natural and authentic materials, and the wish to support local economies (European Crafts Alliance & Ohayō, 2025).

5.5 DOUBLE EVALUATION and the visibility of TENSIONS

Moreover, focusing on how the relation between value proposition and hoped-for customer segment is actually brought about in a craft business makes it possible to identify a number of defining TENSIONS. This is so precisely because it may be difficult, in practice, to make the hoped-for responsiveness work. The values proposed may not be easily communicable, recognizable, affordable, institutionally supported, or economically sustainable in the form intended by the maker; or they may depend on forms of craft practice that are themselves difficult to sustain or communicate. These tensions are intensified by the fact that some of the values craft businesses seek to offer are difficult to render legible within conventional business tools. Accordingly, Friedman et al. (2025) show that many maker entrepreneurs value community, sustainability and creative identity alongside sales, and that traditional tools centered on assets, liabilities, profit and loss often fail to track these concerns.

We therefore do not aim to fully inscribe the craft business cases by means of the BMC building blocks alone. Rather, we use the canvas in a double evaluative movement: first, to ask how the BMC theoretically describes the craft business; and second, to ask how the craft business empirically resists or challenges that description. This enables a kind of DOUBLE EVALUATION between normative claims directed at the model (“our business does not work as your model prescribes”) and normative claims directed at the business (“your business does not behave like a business is supposed to behave”). Without deciding in advance which of these claims should be treated as universally correct, the interplay between them allows some of the tensions characteristic of craft business to become visible in the individual case. At the same time, because the BMC asks relatively general questions and because craft businesses share certain recurring features, some of these tensions may also prove relevant across a broader class of craft businesses.

5.6 CRAFT VALUE PROPOSITION: Product, service, and shared experience

In this respect, the case studies are approached through a small set of analytical devices. First, we draw on the idea that craft business may often involve a SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension, insofar as it may pursue broader social, cultural, ecological, or place-based aims through economic activity. Second, we approach craft business through a notion of MULTIPLE VALUE rather than through economic value alone. Third, we use the BMC as a first descriptive language and as an identifier of areas of tension, without treating it as exhaustive. Fourth, we focus especially on the relation between value proposition and hoped-for customer segment as a fundamental articulation of the business. Finally, in order to specify what is being proposed in many craft cases, we work with the categories of product, service, and shared experience.

When emphasizing “shared experience” as an important part of a craft value proposition, including encountering craft in the making, the exercise of skill, and the presentation of traditions drawn upon (see examples in the cases below), we do not treat experience as belonging primarily to the customer. In parts of the customer value proposition literature, experience is still often approached mainly from the customer side, for example when Smith and Wheeler (2002) emphasize the importance of designing and delivering a branded customer experience. At the same time, Payne et al. (2008) show that the literature has moved beyond a purely supplier-determined account of value propositions toward more transitional and mutually determined perspectives that place greater emphasis on customer experience, value-in-use, reciprocal benefits, resource-sharing and cocreation. We take that movement one step further in relation to craft. More specifically, we suggest that, in many craft settings, experience is not best understood as something designed by the maker for the customer alone, but as something shared between them in the encounter through which craft value is formed.

In this sense, a craft value proposition often entails not only a “product”, such as functional objects, artistic works, or commissioned pieces, or a “service”, such as workshops, courses, shared studio access, or repair, but also a shared experience. This shared experience involves the craft maker as a facilitating participant and the potential customer as a co-participant in the same event of craft value formation. These three expressions of the craft value proposition often follow one another. For example, encountering the craft making process in the workshop environment (experience) can lead both to buying a functional object or an artistic piece (product) and then to taking a course to learn more about the craft in question (service). Yet they can also occur more independently, since products may be bought without services, and experiences may be shared without purchases, making the three expressions empirically and analytically separable. For this reason, we use the categories of product, service and experience to indicate the craft value propositions present in the cases described below, with an emphasis on some of the tensions that the differences and the possible lack of interaction between them might give rise to.

5.7 Articulating the TENSIONS of business models for craft

What the preceding discussion has sought to establish is not a new business model for craft, nor a revised BMC to be substituted for the existing one. Nor, however, has it remained at the level of a merely external critique of standard business-model thinking. The point has rather been to develop a way of reading craft business through business-model language while also exposing the limits of that language when it is confronted with the kinds of value, relations and commitments that craft businesses often have to hold together. In that sense, the preceding discussion has been analytical in a double way: it has clarified certain categories at a more general level, but it has also prepared them for use at a more concrete one.

This is the sense in which the categories introduced above now change status. In the analytical discussion, CRAFT VALUE PROPOSITION, HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER, SOCIALLY FORMATIVE, MULTI-VALUE, and the selective use of BMC categories were established as ways of clarifying what may be at stake in craft business beyond a narrowly revenue-centred account. In the cases, these same categories no longer remain general clarifications but remerge as empirical analytical categories. That is, they are taken up only insofar as they help articulate what is actually going on in the concrete practices under consideration: in particular objects and services, in situated forms of experience, in local commitments, in temporal constraints, in embodied skills, in customer relations, and in the frictions that arise when such elements have to be made to hold together as a business.

This also means that the cases are not treated as illustrations of a prior theoretical framework. The point is not to show that a set of cases “fit” categories already settled in advance, nor to demonstrate that the cases can simply be translated into a completed canvas. The categories are carried into the material in a weaker and more productive sense than that. They are used where they help make the practices more sharply intelligible, and they recede where they do not. In this way, the movement from the analytical section to the case analyses is neither one of deduction nor one of application in any strong sense. It is a movement from more general analytical clarification to more concrete analytical articulation.

At the same time, what is gained in the cases is not merely a set of “examples” for earlier claims. It is through the cases that the analytical categories begin to encounter resistance, variation, density, and overlap. This is especially important because it is only at the level of concrete practice that one can see how different kinds of value may depend on one another unevenly, how particular forms of viability may come under pressure from the very commitments that define the business, and how certain business-model categories may prove more or less useful depending on the case.

6.0 Introduction to the case analyses

The following case analyses concern 9 short cases (3 per 3 ecosystems), plus one extended case:

- Venice with 3 cases: Atelier 23, Atelier Volante & Fablab
- Bornholm with 3 cases: Christina Schou, InKyong Lee & Baltic Sea Glass
- Dals Långed & Fengersfors, ecosystem analysis: Not Quite, Open Wood, Studio Växt
- Bassano del Grappa & Nove with 3 cases: Alberto Scodro, Elena Rausse & Bruno Testa, & Cuko Ceramics

Here, they examine how particular craft practices are configured as businesses without assuming in advance that they can be adequately described through conventional business-model language alone, represented by the Business Model Canvas (BMC) described above. The point of departure is that a craft business is not only a matter of selling something to a customer, but of organizing a more complex relation between what is being proposed as valuable, the people to whom that proposition is directed, and the concrete means through which such a proposition can be developed over time. For this reason, the cases are read not only in terms of market offer and customer demand, but through the broader question of how value, viability, relation and constraint are composed in practice.

A central analytical concern throughout is therefore the relation between CRAFT VALUE PROPOSITION and HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER (see details above). This relation matters because a craft business often depends on more than the existence of a market in the abstract. It depends on a more specific kind of responsiveness. What is being proposed may not only be a product in the narrow sense, but also a service, an experience, a relation to place, a story of material or heritage, or an invitation to value certain qualities differently. Likewise, the relevant “customer” may not simply be anyone willing to pay, but someone willing to respond to this fuller proposition in the way the practice depends on. The cases therefore ask not only what is being offered, but what kind of person, participant, visitor, buyer, learner, collector, or even public in a broader sense, the practice seems to require if its proposition of value is to become workable in the intended way.

The cases are also approached on the assumption that many craft businesses cannot be understood adequately through economic value alone. Economic viability remains necessary, and none of the cases escape that fact. Yet what is at stake in them is often broader: cultural continuity, social relation, ecological concern, local embeddedness, education or the preservation and renewal of skills and ways of making. In some cases, the practice is also oriented toward shaping or suggesting how customers, participants, or local publics come to value objects, processes, places, or relations differently. The analyses therefore carry forward the earlier claim that craft business may involve both a MULTI-VALUE logic and, in some cases, a SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension. These terms are not used here as abstract labels placed on top of the material, but as ways of clarifying what is concretely at stake in the cases themselves.

This also affects how business model-language is used. The BMC is not employed as a complete or exhaustive template, and the cases do not proceed by filling in every block in turn. Rather, the canvas functions as an initial descriptive vocabulary that helps articulate different aspects of the practices where it is useful to do so. In some cases, the main analytical pressure falls on VALUE PROPOSITION and HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER. In others, KEY RESOURCE, KEY ACTIVITY, CHANNEL, or the relation between PRODUCT, SERVICE, and shared EXPERIENCE becomes more decisive. What matters is not completeness, but whether these terms make the practice more intelligible. The analyses are therefore selective by design: they bring into the foreground only those categories that help clarify what the business is trying to do, what it depends on, and where it comes under pressure.

For that reason, the case descriptions below move in a broadly shared sequence without becoming uniform. They begin from the practice and its main orientation, then turn to what is being proposed and to whom, before drawing out the means, conditions, and relations through which this configuration is sustained. From there, the analyses make more explicit the TENSIONS already present in the material. These tensions are not treated as accidental frictions or as defects that could simply be removed by better management. They are among the conditions under which craft businesses become viable, remain coherent, and risk losing what they depend on. A business may need tourism while also being threatened by tourism. It may depend on locality while being constrained by that same embeddedness. It may seek growth while being damaged by the forms growth would require.

6.1 Context of Venice, Italy

Venice has been chosen as one of the HEPHAESTUS craft ecosystems for several reasons. It has a long and still thriving tradition of craftsmanship. Yet over-tourism and the impact of new technologies have changed the city. Overcrowding, changing infrastructures, and consumer behaviours have made Venice less livable. Therefore, the arts and craft sector is impacted, as long-standing crafts are often replaced by mass-produced souvenirs.

At the same time, Venice is frequently invoked in academic literature as a paradigmatic site of the Anthropocene, the epoch in which humanity's planetary impact has become a "geophysical force" (Robin & Steffen, 2007). In Venice, then, the entanglement of human activity and environmental processes becomes materially visible. The city is highly vulnerable to sea-level rise and flooding, known as acqua alta, while lagoon degradation places Venice at the forefront of climate change impacts (Seraphin et al., 2018).

Venice exemplifies the impacts of the Anthropocene through the convergence of centuries of lagoon engineering, intensified tourism, and fossil-fuel-driven global warming in a fragile socio-ecological system. Here, climate change appears as a lived urban condition and resembles what Lazarus (2008) characterizes as a "super wicked problem," defined by urgency, temporal displacement, and institutional inadequacy.

Through our empirical investigations, it became clear that ecological and environmental factors such as rising sea levels are not the most pressing concern for Venetians. Rather, the dominant fear concerns the loss of heritage as a result of over-tourism. The traditional artisans we worked with, who are integral to Venice's identity, increasingly find themselves displaced by the consequences of over-tourism, with some feeling compelled to give up their workshops to souvenir shops. Through this process, centuries-old local knowledge is often forfeited (Costa, 2024).

Venice thus faces profound social transformations linked to over-tourism and depopulation. Over-tourism has been shown to generate both environmental and social over-capacity, affecting residents' quality of life and accelerating the commodification of urban space (Bertocchi & Visentin, 2019). Further, Venice is shaped by short-term visitor cycles, day-trips, cruise tourism, and recurring large-scale cultural events. Such dynamics privilege temporary consumption over everyday habitation, placing pressure on residents, local services and non-tourism activities (Hospers, 2019).

This dynamic is amplified by the long-standing cultural narrative of Venice as a “dying city,” which reinforces perceptions of decline while coexisting with the city's continued attraction as a global tourist destination (Busacca et al., 2025). The resulting tensions between ecological fragility, economic dependency on tourism, and resident depopulation form the structural conditions within which contemporary Venetian craftsmanship must operate. Here, craft practices often emerge as situated responses to intertwined environmental, economic, and cultural pressures. This sets the stage for the following three cases we chose to engage with in this deliverable. The findings have emerged through the past two years of research in Venice, which took place in various forms.

6.1.1 Atelier 23

Atelier 23 is a small Venetian craft business founded in 2020 by Fosca Parisi. Atelier 23 focuses on designing and producing bespoke wedding dresses and garments for special occasions. In doing so, the atelier reflects Fosca's combination of hands-on craftsmanship and a more reflective, artistic understanding of fashion. Her work centers on creating dresses that allow clients to feel beautiful, comfortable, and distinct, while also questioning established norms within the fashion industry. Rather than adhering to the traditional white wedding dress, Parisi experiments with colour and design in ways that encourage rewearing the dress after the ceremony. A recurring source of inspiration in her work is Venice itself, and this relation to the city becomes materially embedded in the dresses she creates.

The value proposition of Atelier 23 has several expressions, and these should be kept distinct. At one level, it concerns the product itself: wedding dresses that are tailored, made-to-order, custom-made, and personalized according to specific preferences, resulting in unique pieces for each client. At another level, it includes a service dimension, since the atelier does not simply deliver a finished object but accompanies the client through consultation, fitting, design, and adjustment. At a third level, it clearly includes experience. Central to the studio's value proposition is the facilitation of an emotionally resonant customer experience, in which the wearer can express a sense of self through the garment.

The atelier therefore offers more than a dress; it also offers a process and a way of moving through that process.

This proposition is further shaped by a strong commitment to localized production. The atelier's mission emphasizes localized production as far as possible, with fabrics and garments sourced primarily from Italy and Europe. In the design and making process, Fosca frequently draws on her professional network and collaborates with artisans in Venice. This is part of what gives the work its value. The dresses are not only aesthetic objects, but also carry something of Venetian craftsmanship, the city's cultural heritage, and the artisanal relations through which they are produced.

Another defining feature of Parisi's practice is her effort to encourage clients to prioritize high-quality fabrics and consider reusing the dress after the wedding. The value proposition thus reaches beyond the immediate event and extends toward duration and afterlife.

This already makes clear that the business cannot be understood in economic terms alone. Economic value is necessary, but it is not the only value at stake. The dress carries aesthetic, social, and cultural value, and to some degree ecological value, insofar as quality, reuse, and resistance to disposability are built into the practice. The point is not merely that these values coexist, but that the atelier depends on keeping them in a particular relation. The customer segment is, in one sense, quite clear. The customer segment of Atelier 23 comprises primarily tourists who get married in Venice and who have the budget to spend a significant amount on weddings and dresses. But this does not yet capture the full business relation. The hoped-for customer is narrower and more demanding than the market category alone suggests. The atelier is not simply directed toward anyone willing to purchase a wedding dress in Venice. It is directed toward someone who can respond to the combined proposition of product, service, experience, locality, and craft.

A first major tension emerges here. This is a very specific niche market and definitively poses frictions. On the one hand, Fosca's business financially depends on over-tourism and Venice's attractiveness. On the other hand, she operates within an economic structure shaped by tourism, which contributes to the broader pressures placed on small, locally owned craft businesses in Venice to prioritize fast-produced goods and souvenir-oriented products over slower, artisanal practices. The atelier depends on a tourism-based economy while also trying to resist some of the forms of acceleration and simplification that such an economy tends to produce.

This tension becomes clearer in the way the atelier's value logic is described. Atelier 23 operates according to what we can call a multi-dimensional value logic rather than a purely economic one. Fosca frames value creation as an intertwinement of economic, social, cultural, and implicitly ecological dimensions. Yet these different types of value are not all equally important. Cultural and social value set the boundaries and are essential for the business, while economic value is restrained by the necessity of operating within these boundaries. Economic viability remains necessary, but it does not function as the sole organizing principle. It is treated more as an enabling condition than as the final measure of the business.

A second tension emerges around place and sourcing. The sourcing logic at Atelier 23, which prioritizes local garments and fabrics, reveals a strong territorial embeddedness. Prioritizing Venetian materials and collaborations with local craft makers means that supply-chain decisions are shaped less by cost than by identity, sustainability, and cultural continuity. The atelier does not merely draw symbolic value from Venice as a backdrop. It helps reproduce Venice as a meaningful craft place through material and relational practice.

At the same time, this embeddedness introduces constraints. Atelier 23 strongly relies on local networks and materials, and therefore its flexibility in sourcing is limited. This limits cost adjustments and restricts opportunities for scaling and growing. What strengthens authenticity also narrows strategic options. A third tension concerns participation and temporality. Atelier 23's value proposition is to a large degree built around involving customers in the entire design and production process, thereby cultivating a very personal experience while simultaneously bringing the customer close to craftsmanship as a practice. The dress is framed as the outcome of a shared journey rather than simply a transactional exchange.

Yet this ideal is difficult to sustain under the actual conditions of the customer relation. Most customers, as explained by Fosca, are tourists who are temporarily in Venice for their wedding. At the same time, the production process of a wedding dress is lengthy and complex, resulting in an inevitable gap between the ideal of deepening engagement and the realities of time management, attention, and distance. What appears here is not merely a practical difficulty, but also a problem of temporal navigation: product, service, and experience do not unfold according to the same rhythm, and the business must hold them together anyway.

Something socially formative is also at stake here, though on a modest scale. The atelier does not only respond to an existing demand for wedding dresses. It also seeks to shape another way of valuing dress, event, craft, and place. It encourages quality over throughput, process over immediacy, and possible reuse over one-time consumption. In that sense, the customer is not treated simply as the bearer of fixed preferences, but as someone who may be guided toward a different responsiveness to what the atelier proposes. This points toward a certain educationability in the customer relation, even if that term is only fully developed later.

What comes into view here is therefore a business that must hold together several difficult relations at once: between product, service, and experience; between a tourism-driven market and a slower craft practice; between local embeddedness and strategic flexibility; and between economic viability and the broader values that define what the atelier is willing to become. These tensions are not incidental. They are among the conditions under which Atelier 23 exists as a business at all.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- How participatory can a craft process be when clients are geographically distant and time-constrained? Could a part of this be digitized?
- How can the depth, duration, and complexity of a production process be meaningfully communicated when clients are present for only limited stages?
- Can slowness, attentiveness, and process transparency be maintained within economic environments that reward speed and efficiency?
- How do you ensure that the product, after purchase, is treated safely and sustainably (e.g. recycled, upcycled, gifted to charity etc.)

6.1.2 Atelier Volante

Atelier Volante is a craft workshop in Venice specializing in the production of traditional papier-mâché masks, a historically significant cultural symbol of Venice and its annual carnival. Atelier Volante is a family-owned business that continues long-standing artisanal traditions while simultaneously incorporating contemporary artistic interpretations into its designs. Sofia Sarria, owner of the business, preserves the various methodologies of traditional Venetian mask-making while introducing novel motifs that differentiate her work clearly from the mass-produced souvenir masks sold throughout the city of Venice. She sells the masks online through her webshops and in her physical shop. In addition to her papier-mâché production, Sofia conducts workshops in which participants learn about the mask-making process, as well as broader educational elements such as the historical, cultural, and artistic significance of the craft. The atelier therefore functions as both a retail space and a site of cultural transmission. Sofia combines production, education, and community engagement within tourism-driven Venice.

The value proposition of Atelier Volante is therefore not exhausted by the mask as product alone, even though the masks remain central. The atelier offers handmade papier-mâché masks that draw their force from Venetian tradition while also being marked by Sofia Sarria's own artistic interpretation. At the same time, the proposition also includes service in the form of workshops, through which visitors encounter not only the making process but the wider historical and cultural significance of the craft.

The business thus depends on more than the sale of objects. It also depends on whether the masks can be received as embodiments of craft skill, Venetian heritage, and artistic distinction rather than as one more version of the souvenir (see Figure 5). By preserving traditional techniques while also experimenting with materials and motifs, Atelier Volante sustains an artistically distinctive approach whose creativity and tacit, practice-based knowledge are difficult for competitors to replicate at scale (Beverland, 2005).

Sofia's business contributes to the preservation of an endangered tradition of artisanal mask-making, once one of Venice's most historically important economic activities, which is now often displaced by cheap, industrially produced souvenir masks made for tourists. That

wider commitment matters to the proposition itself. The masks are valuable not only because they can be worn or displayed, but because they carry a relation to Venice that is historical, material, and still actively made.

This gives the business a multi-value orientation too. Economic value remains necessary, since the atelier must sell masks and sustain its activities. Yet the work also carries cultural value through the preservation and reinterpretation of Venetian mask-making, social value through teaching and community engagement, and a more place-bound symbolic value through its attachment to Venice as a living craft environment rather than a purely touristic image. The important point is not simply that these values coexist, but that the atelier depends on keeping them in relation without allowing the economic one to flatten the others.

The hoped-for customer is correspondingly more particular than a broad customer segment such as tourists, local Venetians, or online buyers. The atelier does not depend only on someone willing to buy a mask. It depends on someone able to distinguish between artisanal work and mass-produced imitation, and willing to respond to the mask as something carrying heritage, skill, and interpretation. That is one reason the workshops matter so much. They do not only generate activity around the product, but help cultivate the kind of attentiveness on which the fuller proposition depends.

A first tension arises between tradition and innovation. It concerns the balance between tradition and innovation. The atelier's legitimacy and recognizability are anchored in the authenticity of Venetian heritage and in the continuity of family-based artisanal practice, yet sustaining relevance in a highly saturated souvenir market also requires stylistic development and experimentation (Shafi et al., 2021). Sofia navigates this balance by retaining core craft techniques while introducing new motifs, illustrations, and material explorations.

The challenge is that an overemphasis on tradition can risk aesthetic stagnation, whereas too much innovation can weaken the symbolic link to Venice that underpins the product's cultural credibility and market differentiation (Zhu & Rahman, 2025). The business therefore has to hold together recognizability and renewal at the same time, since either one pushed too far would damage what gives the atelier its distinctiveness.

A second tension appears around comparability in the market. It concerns cultural value versus market comparability. The masks are presented as embodiments of heritage and craft skill; however, they still compete directly with cheaper, industrially produced souvenirs that visually resemble authentic products (Swanson & Timothy, 2012). This is one of the places where ordinary business-model language begins to strain in this case. The masks can still be described through value proposition, customer segment, and channels, but the problem is not only how to sell them. It is also how to sustain the difference between artisanal and industrial value in a market where visual similarity may hide profound differences in meaning, labor, and continuity.

That pressure is why place-making also matters here. The value of the masks is tied not only to Venice as a brand image, but to Venice as a place where specific craft histories, family traditions, and workshop practices still persist under pressure. The atelier does not

simply draw symbolic force from the city. It also participates in sustaining Venice as a meaningful craft place by continuing one of its distinctive traditions in a form not yet reduced to souvenir logic. The deeper that attachment to place becomes, the more it supports authenticity and cultural credibility, but the more it also binds the business to the conditions of a city shaped by tourism, rent pressure, and commodification.

A third tension concerns time and customer relationships, and has to do with transient versus deep time. Atelier Volante's customers are primarily local Venetians, national customers, and international tourists, each with varying degrees of knowledge about Venetian craft. The relationships Sofia has with her customers are deeply personal, to the highest degree possible with tourists being only temporarily present in Venice. Workshops function as educational spaces where customers learn about history, technique, and heritage.

However, not all customers seek or have time for such engagement. The business depends in part on a slower and deeper mode of relation, one that takes time to build and time to receive. Yet much of the economic environment in Venice is structured by brevity, passing attention, and rapid circulation. Temporal navigation becomes relevant here because the atelier has to move between these different tempos without letting the shorter one consume the longer one.

That same pressure also gives Atelier Volante's practice a form of educationability. The term matters here because part of the value of the atelier depends on whether a visitor or customer can come to value the mask differently through learning. While the workshops are the clearest expression of this, the same relation also extends into the shop and the act of purchase itself. What the atelier hopes for is not merely a transaction, but a customer who can become more responsive to history, technique, and cultural significance through the encounter with the work. In that sense, the business depends not only on selling masks, but on making the grounds for valuing them more legible.

The channels of the business make this even more visible. Atelier Volante uses its physical shop, website, social media, Etsy, and Airbnb workshops as channels to communicate its products and to sell them. The physical studio anchors the brand in Venice, and digital platforms extend its reach beyond the city. That arrangement is productive, but it is not frictionless.

When investigating deeper, we find another tension here: place-based authenticity on the one hand, and digital mediation on the other. The Venetian masks Sofia creates derive symbolic power from being made and purchased in Venice. Expanding digital channels increases resilience and reach. Yet excessive reliance on online sales risks detaching the product from its experiential context. What strengthens resilience may also weaken the place-bound conditions that give the product much of its force.

A socially formative dimension is also present here. For Sofia, her primary intention lies in sustaining her family's craft tradition, safeguarding the artisanal techniques of papier-mâché mask-making, supporting the broader continuity of the local artisan sector, and contributing to the preservation of Venice's cultural identity. The atelier does not only answer a market

demand for decorative or festive masks. It also contributes to shaping what can still count as Venetian mask-making, and to keeping that practice legible as something other than a commercial residue of carnival culture. In that sense, the business is not only selling within an existing environment, but participating in the maintenance of that environment.

What this business has to hold together, then, is not one simple proposition but several difficult relations at once: between tradition and innovation, between artisanal distinction and tourist comparability, between deep relation and transient attention, and between place-based authenticity and digital extension. The masks, the workshops, the physical shop, and the digital channels all matter here, but not in the same way and not without pressure.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ How can innovation be balanced with fidelity to tradition, without undermining or weakening either?
- ★ What alternative customer segments can be targeted to ensure the business does not only rely on tourism flows and seasons?
- ★ Which elements of the craft practices in the business model are non-negotiable, despite economic pressure?
- ★ How can place-based authenticity as a key selling point also be integrated into digital channels?

Figure 5 - Traditional Masks in Venice, Author's own photograph taken in 2022

6.1.3 FabLab

FabLab Venezia belongs to the craft field because it works directly on the conditions of making, even though it does so through digital fabrication rather than through the hand alone. As a Fabrication Lab, the business creates access to a range of low-cost fabrication machines, and it does so within a community-based, peer-production approach (Blikstein, 2013). The FabLab focuses on the digitalization of creative and cultural processes, and what it offers is less a finished object than the ability to move from an idea or a problem to a technically workable way of making.

The VALUE PROPOSITION lies in technological access and know-how, especially in access to 3D printing, scanning, and laser cutting, together with the “explanation power” required to translate institutional or maker needs into workable production pathways. What is being offered here is therefore not only equipment, but a form of technical mediation through which needs can be interpreted, modelled, and turned into processes that others can actually use. The proposition is carried mainly through SERVICE, capability, and translation rather than through PRODUCT alone.

For craft, this means that the machine is not treated as sufficient in itself. 3D printing works as a tool for combining tradition with innovation in ways that remain meaningfully craft because of the irreducible human component in operating, designing and deciding (Alberta et al., 2024; Mongeon, 2015). According to manager Alberta Menegaldo (lead of WP2), it is important to recognize that digital fabrication does not abolish or “compete with” traditional craftsmanship but co-exists with it. Here, skill, authorship, and judgment are kept inside the process even where fabrication is technologically mediated.

One recent work example gives that claim a concrete form: a Venetian sculpture was eroding because of rising water levels in Venice, and FabLab Venezia used 3D printing technology to replicate and preserve it. The work remains tied to craft because form, continuity, and cultural memory still depend on skilled intervention, even though that intervention now passes through scanning, modelling, and digital fabrication rather than through the hand alone. The VALUE PROPOSITION therefore includes a preservation capability together with access and technical capability.

Equally, the FabLab can also be read as an intervention in craft economies which shifts the locus of value from a singular handmade object toward a broader service-and-capability proposition. That shift remains central. Value no longer gathers mainly in the finished object, as it also appears in access, explanation, modelling, repair, prototyping, preservation and in the possibility of enabling others to produce, reproduce, repair, prototype and design.

The FabLab case differs from most of the other cases presented here. It does not only facilitate, support, or open up possibilities of integrating technology and craft in new experimental ways. Doing so, the FabLab Venezia also engages in social innovation (Gasparin et al., 2022; 2020) in a stronger sense than the more modest SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension used elsewhere in the report. Helping to shape how people can value craft, FabLab Venezia’s work is organized around a broader social reconfiguration of access to making, technical capability, conservation work and knowledge-sharing, where

social innovation concerns solutions whose value accrues primarily to society as a whole rather than to the private individual (Phills et al. 2008, p. 39). That stronger orientation is visible here because the benefits of the lab spill beyond the immediate paying client and into a wider field of makers, institutions, conservation actors and publics.

Economic value still matters because the lab has to remain operative, but it does not organize the work on its own. The business model of FabLab does not aim to gain profits. The annual turnover is relatively small, and the financial strategy is merely to keep FabLab running. Alberta describes the value created by the lab as lying somewhere between enabling access to advanced technology, allowing projects to be developed “in a more independent and forward-looking way”, using fewer resources, and supporting sustainability through community, inclusion and knowledge-sharing. She also emphasizes the value of social sustainability, namely that a community is created, that it includes different ideas and people, and that it enables knowledge sharing. The lab is there, as she says, to “serve the citizens.” A MULTI-VALUE logic is therefore unusually explicit in this case because economic, social, cultural, and ecological value are all active in the proposition itself.

The question of who the FabLab is for immediately places ordinary market language under pressure. FabLab’s CUSTOMER SEGMENTS include service-users, craft-makers, museums, and “people in need of conservation” as well as other institutions. Those groups do not form one coherent market role. Museums and public institutions may be paying clients in particular projects, yet they also act as stewards of collective cultural value. Craft-makers may appear as customers, yet they also gain access to tools, knowledge, and production capacity that change what they themselves can do. Those “in need of conservation” stand even further from an ordinary buyer position.

The HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER is therefore not simply a purchaser of services. FabLab Venezia depends on users and partners who can value access, mediation, explanation and technical capability, and who can sometimes treat these as public goods rather than private advantages. That is one reason the original material is right to note a tension between the broad social language of the lab and the narrower reality of its actual clientele. The lab can be read as both democratizing and selective. It lowers barriers of skill, time, equipment access and remains embedded in institutional and project-based relations that may reproduce forms of cultural-sector stratification.

Craft identity becomes even more unstable once the users of the lab are described from inside the practice. Alberta says: “We are digital craft makers even though we are operating with machines. There is still a very important human component”. Craft is thus retained, but retained in altered form. Skill, authorship, legitimacy and authenticity are not discarded, but redistributed across operation, design, decision, explanation and technical translation.

EDUCATIONABILITY takes a distinct form in that setting. Part of the value of FabLab Venezia depends on whether others become able to understand and use digital fabrication differently than before. The lab does not simply provide equipment, but operates and depends on explanation, translation and guided use, so that technical access becomes meaningful capability. That learning relation is not identical with traditional craft teaching, but it matters directly to the proposition and to the craft ecosystem around it.

For craft makers, the FabLab also makes a further set of tensions more visible when they reflect on their own business model and stakeholder landscape. A first TENSION concerns FabLab's own prioritization of institutional actors. Because "real change happens when it is the big ones, municipalities" and because their mission is to "serve the citizens", value creation is partly oriented toward public policy and collective outcomes even when the immediate interaction takes the form of a paid service. A FabLab can therefore function as an enabling partner that opens access to resources, legitimacy, and project opportunities, yet it can also reorient what kinds of projects become worth pursuing, and on what timelines, insofar as "the problem addressed is one dependent on the value judgments of various stakeholders."

A second TENSION appears when digital fabrication enters craft practice as extension rather than replacement. Alberta frames technology as something craft makers are "free to use," and as an extension and not as a counterpart to craftsmanship. Yet the material also records a different response: a hard-to-articulate "loss of value" when making shifts from hands to machines, together with associations to speed, accuracy, and an "aspect of mass production" through identical outputs. For craft makers, this becomes a business-model tension because it affects how value propositions can be credibly narrated, how uniqueness, authenticity, provenance and price can still be justified, and how customers may interpret the meaning of craft under conditions of technologically mediated production.

A third TENSION concerns the kinds of capabilities through which value is created. FabLab Venezia foregrounds capabilities such as prototyping, 3D modelling, digital fabrication, and the translation of needs into workable solutions, and these capabilities reconceive skill, authorship, legitimacy, authenticity in making processes. This matters for sustainable craft because "responsibility" and "sustainability" emerge through the priorities and incentives of several actors such as institutions, municipalities, cultural organizations, publics, and makers, so the tension is not only between market categories and wider cultural, social, and environmental stakes, but also between different ways of defining what craft work is for. In that sense, the FabLab becomes a stakeholder that shifts the terms of business-model reflection itself: who benefits from craft work, what forms of value can be claimed, and what activities and partnerships become necessary for craft livelihoods and sustainable transitions.

FabLab Venezia is useful for business-model reflection in craft because it keeps these tensions active at once. It widens access and remains selective. It extends making and unsettles inherited craft value. It supports conservation, experimentation, and public-oriented capability while depending on institutions, projects, and mediating actors. It therefore presses hard on the limits of standard business-model language, not because the BMC becomes irrelevant, but because the ordinary categories of customer, service, partner, and value do not stay stable for long.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ If FabLab’s digital fabrication technology is used; what changes in my own craft value proposition, and how can this be integrated in storytelling to long-established customers?
- ★ If I treat the FabLab as a key partner, which stakeholders will shape my work the most, and what constraints my own creative autonomy and the kind of projects I can pursue?
- ★ When claiming “sustainable and responsible” craftsmanship, “handmade” - when selling products which involve the use of a FabLab, what is my own concrete sustainability commitment (materials, longevity, local impact, waste...)?

6.2 The Bornholm ecosystem

Bornholm is a Danish island in the Baltic Sea with a strong and still active craft profile, especially in ceramics, glass, textiles and metalwork. Craft on the island is tied not only to heritage and local identity, but also to current questions of sustainability, material reuse and resource-conscious production. Bornholm is also officially recognized as Europe’s first World Craft Region, while BOFA’s Vision 2032 frames the island’s waste system around the aim of ending waste incineration and treating discarded materials as resources to be reused and recycled. These conditions give craft on Bornholm a distinctive setting in which local making, circularity and public sustainability ambitions are unusually closely connected.

At the same time, craft on Bornholm is shaped by the practical limits of island conditions. Many makers work at limited scale, combine several roles within the same practice, and have to navigate seasonality, time pressure, collaboration and the problem of forming viable markets under constrained conditions. The island therefore brings into view a set of tensions in which heritage, local material conditions, circular production and the search for sustainable business forms are tightly interwoven.

These conditions also bring a characteristic set of TENSIONS into view. Craft makers on Bornholm often have to hold together local heritage, circular ambitions, seasonal demand and the practical limits of small-scale production, often while moving between making, teaching, collaboration and other forms of work within the same practice. Their businesses are sustained through different CHANNELS and CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, but also through ecological, territorial, educational, and symbolic forms of value that cannot be reduced to price alone. The following cases from Bornholm therefore do not only show different ways of organizing craft practice on the island, but also different ways in which business-model language comes under pressure when it is confronted with time use, place, learning, circular production, and the viability of resource-conscious making.

Figure 6 - Students from Copenhagen Business School exploring and doing fieldwork at BOFA; Photo taken by authors in 2025

Figure 7 - Waste toilets at BOFA; Photo taken by authors in 2025

6.2.1 Christina Schou

Christina Schou is an established ceramist based in Bornholm and affiliated with the Royal Danish Academy of Glass & Ceramics, where she both teaches and maintains her independent studio practice. She has developed a reputation for experimentation, particularly through her work with recycled and waste-based materials (see Figure 7). Central to her recent practice is the acquisition of a crushing machine, which allows her to reuse fired ceramic waste, glass, and local granite in new clay bodies and glazes. This technological investment has not only expanded her material possibilities but has also positioned her within ongoing discussions on circular production and sustainability in craft. Alongside producing sculptural ceramics exhibited in galleries, Christina conducts workshops, both in-person and online, and is currently developing a sub-brand focused on glazes made from crushed waste and workshops on the same topic, extending her practice into new forms of value creation within the craft ecosystem of Bornholm.

A new **KEY RESOURCE** in Christina Schou's evolving business model is the crushing machine, whose acquisition marked a decisive moment in the development of the practice. Its acquisition marked a decisive moment in her practice, as it allowed her to extend her business model. Its importance lies not only in the addition of another tool, but in the way it changes what can be done with material, what kinds of products and services can emerge from the practice, and how the practice may be sustained over time.

The **VALUE PROPOSITION** is correspondingly broader than before. What Christina Schou proposes as valuable is no longer limited to sculptural ceramic works exhibited in gallery contexts. It now includes new material possibilities, waste-based glazes, knowledge-sharing, and practical workshops hosted at her own pace. The proposition therefore has several expressions. It includes **PRODUCT** in the form of sculptures and, increasingly, glaze mixtures. It includes **SERVICE** in the form of workshops and the transfer of know-how. It also includes a more process-oriented dimension, because the work is valued not only through finished objects, but through the material experimentation and circular thinking that the practice increasingly embodies.

By introducing waste-material crushing as a core activity, Christina's practice resonates with the concept of business model extension (Cavalcante et al., 2011). The crushing machine transformed her **KEY ACTIVITIES** by integrating waste processing directly into her practice and opened possibilities for new products and services. These developments generated new ways of capturing value, not only through use of almost cost-free waste materials and the application of new glazes in sculptures developed from those materials, but also through knowledge-sharing activities and practical workshops hosted at her own pace and by engaging in collaborative exhibitions funded by EU grants (i.e. Ødeland). This extension matters because it broadens both what the business can offer and the ways in which it may remain viable. Economic value is still necessary, but it is no longer the only register through which the practice has to be understood. The crushing machine also supports ecological value through reuse, educational value through workshops and knowledge-sharing, and

artistic value through experimentation with new glaze and material possibilities, so that a MULTI-VALUE logic becomes easier to see in the organization of the practice itself.

The clearest pressure in the case appears when the machine is considered not only as a KEY RESOURCE but in relation to the time required to make it productive. The acquisition of the machine also introduced a new kind of strain regarding her time allocation. Christina's activities already extend beyond sculpture production. She teaches at the Royal Danish Academy, produces gallery work, participates in research projects and craft events, experiments with new materials, applies for funding, and maintains supplier and customer relationships, among other activities. What the machine adds is therefore not one more isolated task, but a whole set of demands within an already crowded practice.

Christina Schou's case shows that the pressure does not lie in time shortage alone, but in having to hold together several temporalities at once: the time of production, experimentation, workshops, teaching, administration, and longer-term development. TEMPORAL NAVIGATION is named here as an emergent category because it captures a pattern that becomes visible in the case itself rather than being obvious from the outset: the need to negotiate between different temporal demands, each of which matters differently to the practice. The category matters beyond this case because comparable tensions can appear across craft businesses, even where they take different forms.

What comes into focus here is the kind of difficulty later gathered under TEMPORAL NAVIGATION: not simple time shortage, but the need to negotiate between different temporal demands within the same practice. Production, experimentation, workshops, teaching, administration, and longer-term development all follow different rhythms and matter differently to the business yet still have to be held together. While the addition of the crushing technology expanded her strategic and material capabilities, it simultaneously increased the demands and divisions of her time, as it has required substantial time investment to work within each of the new areas. Crushing, sorting, testing, adjusting mixtures and ensuring safety in the process are all labour-intensive processes that Christina largely performs herself, although occasionally supported by short-term student assistants. Time therefore appears here not as a neutral background condition, but as one of the main pressures through which the practice has to be organized.

The tension lies in the dual effect of working with the crushing machine. Indeed, it strengthens Christina's capacity for renewal and differentiation, yet its integration requires a substantial redistribution of time. Cavalcante et al. (2011) emphasize that business model extension must be integrated with existing core processes, but the need to expand the concept of time more explicitly as a strategic resource, is still to be addressed. The crushing machine creates value, but how is that value negotiated in the allocation of time? In one-woman businesses or micro-organizations time use is exclusively finite and repeatedly contested. Its evaluation cannot rely on a single metric: revenue per hour, strategic positioning, intrinsic motivation, or long-term capability building may all point in different directions. What comes under pressure here is therefore not only workload, but the whole question of how different temporal claims are weighed against one another when they each appear necessary to the practice.

That question extends beyond the machine itself. Christina Schou is not only a maker producing objects, but also a teacher, workshop facilitator, material developer, collaborator and grant participant, and none of these roles can easily be subtracted from the others without affecting the whole configuration. The practice is sustained through several partially overlapping activities, each contributing differently to viability, identity, and longer-term development.

This becomes especially clear in relation to teaching. For activities such as teaching at the Royal Academy, which she has repeatedly questioned whether she can continue, stepping away is not as simple as it may seem. Being a teacher strongly shapes her professional craft identity. It connects her to students and situates her within the broader craft ecosystem of Bornholm. Teaching is therefore not just another revenue stream, but part of the relation through which the practice holds together. The same activity may function at once as income source, identity anchor, and ecosystem contribution, which again makes the time problem more complex than a simple issue of efficiency.

Sustainability introduces another pressure of its own. Christina Schou's work clearly carries ecological value through reuse, waste-based experimentation, and the redirection of discarded materials into new ceramic forms, but this ecological dimension does not stand alone. It is interwoven with aesthetic experimentation, new product lines, professional positioning and workshop-based knowledge-sharing. Sustainability appears as one pressure among several, since the crushing machine is valuable because it enables circular production while also enabling new materials, new glazes and new revenue possibilities.

PLACE-MAKING may be introduced here as an emergent category, that is, as a term for a recurrent kind of business-model condition that becomes visible through the cases themselves rather than being fully given in advance. In Christina Schou's case, the point is not simply that the practice is located on Bornholm, but that Bornholm enters directly into what the practice is and can become. The use of local granite, the relation to the Royal Academy, the workshop activity and the wider Bornholm craft ecosystem all help sustain the island as a place of ceramic innovation and continuity. Christina Schou's work therefore does not only happen on Bornholm, but also participates in keeping Bornholm meaningful as a craft place, which is why the category becomes useful again in later cases where the relation between business and place takes other forms.

A modest but important SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension is also present. The work reshapes how waste, material experiment, and circular production may be understood within craft practice. That formative dimension is most visible in the workshops and in the developing glaze sub-brand, where material knowledge becomes shareable rather than remaining internal to the studio. A first, lighter version of EDUCATIONABILITY can also be seen here, since part of the value depends on others becoming willing to see waste material, circular practice, and experimentation differently than before.

What this case makes easier to see is a practice that has to hold together KEY RESOURCE expansion and finite time, artistic production and multiple additional roles, ecological experimentation and viable revenue, and product, service, and knowledge-sharing within one still relatively small organization. Christina Schou's case is therefore useful not only in

itself, but because it gives a first clear form to TEMPORAL NAVIGATION and a first lighter form to PLACE-MAKING, both of which return later in different ways.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ How do you prevent overcommitment when your practice spans multiple roles and projects?
- ★ What guides your decisions when prioritizing activities (i.e. income, differentiation, motivation, long-term development)?
- ★ Can you calculate the cost of your time across different activities? How?
- ★ How do you make your time visible and valued, rather than treating it as an unlimited personal reserve?

6.2.2 Inkyong Lee

Inkyong Lee's work differs from a traditional production-oriented craft business, as her ceramic practice is closely tied to reflection and sustainability awareness. She is formally trained in ceramics and previously engaged in small-scale production of functional ware such as cups and vessels. Her current focus has gradually shifted toward experimental and participatory projects. Rather than positioning herself primarily as a business owner, she identifies as an artist who uses craft as a medium to question consumption and the responsibility around it.

Since Inkyong Lee no longer runs her ceramic studio as a continuously producing business, analyzing her value proposition requires expanding what counts as "a business." What persists here is not continuous output, but a practice that still organizes value through skill, encounter, and reflection. The case therefore matters because it clarifies how craft may remain economically and socially legible even when regular production is no longer its main centre.

This has consequences for how VALUE PROPOSITION should be understood in this case. For Inkyong, the value proposition lies less in producing or supplying ceramic objects and more in cultivating a different way of relating to such creations among those who encounter her work. Ceramic objects remain important, but they do not carry the proposition alone. The work also depends on the encounter through which objects become occasions for reflection about consumption, labour and responsibility.

She speaks about craft as a means of raising awareness around consumption patterns, even to the point of encouraging people not to buy. For example, in her exhibition *Take (##)* for the European Ceramic Context in Bornholm, she placed several cups on a table for visitors to take freely, but only after confronting them by asking questions on the motives of taking a cup with them, and other reflective questions about need, desire, and responsibility. The object is therefore placed within a situation that makes taking it inseparable from reflecting on why one takes it and what kind of relation to need, desire, and responsibility is being enacted.

The same orientation appears in her refusal to let demand determine output. An example of this orientation is her refusal to expand production despite receiving requests to do so. She explicitly states that production on demand, strict delivery schedules and batch manufacturing do not align with her way of working. Increasing output simply to meet demand contradicts the purpose she assigns to her craft. For her, growth of this nature would compromise the coherence of her values and the integrity of her practice. The work therefore includes a limit on what kind of business it is willing to become.

Economic value remains relevant, but it does not function as the organizing principle. Ethical, cultural and ecological concerns are equally active, and they are not arranged as secondary additions to an otherwise standard business. A MULTI-VALUE logic is therefore present here too, though in a form quite different from some of the other cases presented here. The practice depends less on expanding output but very explicitly on preserving the relation between purpose, an insistence on restraint and the way objects are encountered. EDUCATIONABILITY can be introduced here as another emergent category. The term is meant to describe cases in which part of the value of the practice depends on another person becoming able, or willing, to value the object, process or practice differently than before. In Inkyong Lee's practice, this is not a secondary feature but one of the main conditions under which the work matters at all. The practice depends on connecting with a recipient who can pause, reflect, and enter a different relation to consumption, labour and material process. The category is useful beyond this case because similar learning relations may return later in other craft businesses, even where they take different forms.

Inkyong's work directly challenges what can be called a "parasitic logic" (Gasparin et al., 2020) in which material and ecological dependencies remain abstract and invisible in contemporary production systems. By making visible the time, labor, skill, and material resources embedded in each object, she seeks to alter how objects are treated and valued. Much of the value of the work therefore depends on whether the encounter succeeds in making these dimensions perceptible.

This also sharpens the question of the HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER. Inkyong Lee emphasizes that customers frequently ask who made the piece, where she lives and inquire about her educational background. The hoped-for customer is not simply anyone willing to acquire a ceramic object, but someone willing to care about origin, making, biography, and embedded labour. The practice depends on a responsiveness that is slower and more reflective than ordinary purchase alone.

A SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension is equally clear. The work does not only respond to existing preferences. It also reshapes how objects, consumption, and responsibility may be approached. Craft consumption here involves learning about how objects are made, where materials come from, and what kinds of labour are embedded in them. The practice therefore participates in forming another moral and cultural relation to them.

A first TENSION emerges around growth and coherence. This orientation implicitly narrows the customer segment. Her practice seems directed toward participants willing to accept limits in availability and volume, and who would value insight into production processes.

Inkyong's practice positions customers as someone willing to learn, including becoming aware that not all forms of demand will be satisfied, and not all expectations will be accommodated. The practice may become more coherent by refusing certain forms of growth, but that coherence also narrows the field of responsiveness on which it depends.

A second TENSION emerges around production and refusal. What would be compromised if production were increased to meet demand? Under what conditions does producing less become a responsible choice rather than a problem to be solved? Is growth aligned with your purpose, or does it risk undermining it? These questions arise directly from a practice that no longer treats expansion as self-evidently desirable.

A third TENSION concerns the status of the object itself. The ceramic piece remains present, but it no longer functions only as a product to be bought and used. It also works as a vehicle for reflection, delay, and reevaluation. VALUE PROPOSITION can still be named here, but it must be understood differently, because it lies in how it interrupts and questions the relation between object and recipient.

What this case brings forward is a craft practice that must hold together several difficult relations at once: between object and reflection, between demand and refusal, between viability and restraint, and between making as production and making as a way of educating perception. EDUCATIONABILITY matters here because the work depends, in part, on another person becoming able to receive the object in the fuller terms the practice asks of it.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ What would be compromised if production were increased to meet demand?
- ★ Under what conditions does producing less become a responsible choice rather than a problem to be solved?
- ★ Is growth aligned with your purpose, or does it risk undermining it?
- ★ Who is your practice for, and how do you speak to them?
- ★ Should all forms of demand be met? What is lost, or protected, when some forms of demand are declined?
- ★ How can limits to growth be articulated as responsibility rather than as failure?

6.2.3 Baltic Sea Glass

Baltic Sea Glass is a hot glass studio located on the rocky coast just southeast of Gudhjem, Bornholm, and has operated for more than 40 years. The studio, originally housed in a former chicken coop, now consists of a gallery, shop, and open workshop where visitors can observe glassblowing processes several days a week. Founded by Danish glass artist Maibritt Jönsson and American glassblower Pete Hunner, the studio developed a distinctive aesthetic inspired by natural motifs and movement, which continues to shape its artistic identity. The production is carried out by a small team of skilled glassblowers who

collectively uphold a high standard of Danish glass art while exploring technical and formal possibilities within the hot glass medium (Figure 8).

In this business, VALUE PROPOSITION and CHANNEL are closely intertwined. Baltic Sea Glass relies on in-person interactions as the primary way of communicating its value proposition, and where sales happen most often. In contrast to faster-paced and digitally mediated sales, this approach unfolds at a slower tempo and remains anchored to the space of their studio in Bornholm. BSG's value proposition relies in the production of high-quality glass-blown pieces, which are presented as inseparable from the legacy of the island, its landscape and cultural history. Yet the value offered through the work is not object-centered only. The value offered through Baltic Sea Glass's work is therefore not object-centered only but based in the narratives that can mostly emerge through encounters of the visitors with the craft makers, the studio setting, and by listening to the stories of practices on Bornholm's glassmaking tradition. The product matters, but so does the encounter, the telling, and the experience through which the object becomes meaningful.

This means that the VALUE PROPOSITION cannot be understood through PRODUCT alone. In this sense, the value proposition is not realized only through a product or a service, but equally through storytelling as a practice of sharing what Gigerenzer (2015, p. 362) calls "general knowledge among the people," inviting customers to construct their own understanding and appreciation of the craft. A conventional SERVICE element is less pronounced here than in some of the other cases. Baltic Sea Glass does not primarily build its relation to the public through courses, consultancy, or a clearly distinct service offer. Rather, the proposition is carried above all by the relation between PRODUCT and EXPERIENCE: between the object and the situated encounter through which the object is perceived, narrated, and sometimes purchased. There is also a lighter form of EDUCATIONABILITY in this value proposition, since storytelling and situated encounter do not simply present the object but invite visitors to learn how to value it through process, place and craft continuity.

Baltic Sea Glass sales history reinforces this point as their transactions occur primarily in the studio. As Michael Brandt, the founder, puts it, the intention is not primarily "to sell but to tell a story," with sales understood as an emergent outcome rather than the central objective. The studio operates as a site of experience and relation, not only as a point of economic transactions. Visitors are invited to hear the history behind the brand, and to witness the process of glassblowing if there are glassblowers actively working in that moment. Michael notes that even when purchases are deferred, such encounters may cultivate long-term attachment and transform visitors into ambassadors of the brand, although this too may be an emergent rather than an intended outcome. The studio, gallery, shop, and workshop do not simply move a product toward a customer. They actively shape what kind of value the product can have.

This also shapes the HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER. The hoped-for customer is not simply an immediate buyer, but someone willing to stay, observe, listen, and perhaps return later to the work with greater attachment. Responsiveness is not reducible to immediate purchase. It may also take the form of appreciation, return visits, recommendations, and a stronger relation to the studio and its story.

A first major TENSION emerges here around the CHANNEL itself. If value is communicated primarily through situated encounters, storytelling, and the atmosphere of the workshop, then the business is also structurally exposed to markets increasingly shaped by digital scalability. This tension raises direct questions, such as: How can storytelling and relational engagement be positioned as central components of value? How does a place- and interaction-based business position itself within markets increasingly shaped by digital scalability? The question is not simply whether Baltic Sea Glass should digitize more, but what happens when a place- and interaction-based business is compelled to position itself within market forms that privilege circulation, speed and distance over situated relation.

A second TENSION emerges when one turns from VALUE PROPOSITION and CHANNEL toward KEY RESOURCES and KEY ACTIVITIES. From the point of view of key resources and key activities, other tensions arise. Firstly, the fragility and embodied nature of skilled labor. Glassblowing expertise is scarce in Europe (Morris, 2021; Gammelby, 2024; Heritage Crafts, n.d.), and the work is physically demanding. Glassblowers can develop heavy pain in their wrists and need to take long breaks between shifts, or sometimes illnesses in the wrists can come unsuspectedly incapacitating them for a longer time. Michael Brandt emphasized that sustaining the craft requires careful management of bodily capacity to prevent burnout or long-term injury. In that sense, the glassblower's mental and physical health becomes a central yet vulnerable element of the business. Its sustainability can hardly be measured or standardized, since each craftsperson's condition and capacity differ and call for different forms of care.

This is also where TEMPORAL NAVIGATION begins to matter. These intricacies and temporalities in the care from the organization towards the makers and the environment that sustains them, can become invisible in economic abstractions (de la Bellacasa, 2017) even though they are integral to the maintenance of the practice. Time is more than only production time here. It is also recovery time, bodily limit, pacing, and the time required to sustain skill without burnout. The business does not simply depend on skilled labor in the abstract. It depends on the continued bodily possibility of performing that labor under conditions that vary from one person to another.

A third TENSION emerges around the collective organization of the studio. It appears around questions of authorship and the collective discipline of glass blowing within Baltic Sea Glass. The studio operates as a collective organization, and individual craft makers contribute their own artistic sensibilities and skills to the production process. Yet, for Baltic Sea Glass to maintain a coherent aesthetic identity, it requires individual glassblowers to consciously limit personal expression. This negotiation between individual subjectivity and collective coherence is not external to the work but belongs to the conditions under which the work can appear as recognizably Baltic Sea Glass at all.

The collective is thus not a neutral structure, but depends on ongoing mutual recognition, care, and respect. If not properly nurtured, this shared subjectivity of the working collective can weaken, affecting both internal dynamics and the quality of the work produced. The richness of Baltic Sea Glass pieces is hence inseparable from the internal ecology that sustains them. Rather than viewing these collective dynamics as external to the business

model, they can be understood as part of the key resources of craft-based organizations. Elements such as shared identity, internal relations, and practices of care constitute essential conditions for value creation. The case therefore also presses on the limits of how neatly KEY RESOURCES, KEY ACTIVITIES, and organizational relations can be separated.

PLACE-MAKING is also already visible here, even if only lightly marked. Bornholm's landscape, the continuity of glassmaking, the open workshop and the studio's own physical setting all enter into the value of the work. More than only operating on Bornholm, Baltic Sea Glass brings value to the island's craft recognition, through the relation between glass objects, situated encounters, and stories of local continuity.

What comes into view here is therefore a business that aims to hold together several difficult relations at once: between VALUE PROPOSITION and CHANNEL, between product and experience, between situated storytelling and digital market logics, between embodied skill and long-term viability, and between collective identity and individual contribution. These tensions are not incidental. They are among the conditions under which Baltic Sea Glass exists as a business at all.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ How can storytelling and relational engagement be positioned as central components of value?
- ★ How does my place- and interaction-based business position itself within markets increasingly shaped by digital scalability?
- ★ How do you account for the time required to maintain skills, prevent burnout, and sustain long-term practice?
- ★ What forms of internal care (for bodies, skills, relationships) are essential to sustaining your practice?
- ★ How do you navigate the dynamics that sustain the creative richness in your organization, while balancing between individual artistic expression and a coherent brand identity?
- ★ How do you preserve space for individual artistic contributions while safeguarding the shared vision and internal relationships that hold the organization together?

Figure 8 - Glassblowers at Baltic Sea Glass. Retrieved from: <https://www.balticseaglass.com/en>

6.3 The Dals Långed and Fengersfors ecosystem

Dals Långed and Fengersfors are two closely connected rural towns in the western part of Sweden. As a craft ecosystem it distinguishes itself from the others in two respects in relation to entrepreneurship: First of all, the institutional presence of dedicated craft and craft-supporting organizations, i.e. the professional school, the Academy of Art and Design at the University of Gothenburg Campus Steneby and the regional development hub Mötesplats Steneby; secondly, the spirit of collective entrepreneurship, which is manifested in several instances of craft makers collaborating in more or less permanent structures and of tackling problems and market opportunities collectively. These two peculiarities of the functioning of this ecosystem are in symbiosis with each other both practically and culturally, constituting the marks of a sort of entrepreneurial infrastructure of this craft ecosystem, that is, a configuration of KEY RESOURCES and KEY PARTNERSHIPS. While we have previously stressed the importance of educational institutional presence (Deliverable 1.1), this section focuses on collective entrepreneurship.

This collective organization of resources, partnerships, and ways of staying in place makes PLACE-MAKING relevant from the outset. What is at stake in this ecosystem is not only that

craft takes place in Dals Långed and Fengersfors, but that collective entrepreneurship helps make these towns into places where craft can be lived, sustained and developed (Korsgaard et al., 2015).

In the 19th century, Fengersfors was a hub for iron and, later, pulp, and paper production, but this production decreased with the expansion of plastic and the main paper mill in Fengersfors ceased its operations in 1978, marking the end of an industrial era. It is here, in this industrial heritage site, that in the beginning of 2000s a group of craft makers and artists, many of whom had studied at the Academy of Art and Design Campus Steneby in Dals Långed, got together and started a collective. Their desire was to make the place a place where they could stay and work, sharing not only workshops, but also ideas and practices. They started Not Quite, which is today a landmark in Sweden's contemporary art and craft scene and renowned internationally both for its artistic initiatives and for its collective entrepreneurship. Not Quite is, for instance, part of the Trans European Halles Network.

Today, Not Quite hosts around 80 artists, most of which live in the local area of Fengersfors and surroundings. The premises of Not Quite are organized in collective workshops, a garden, a bakery, a café, a bistro, a crafts shop, and galleries showcasing the artists' work. From a BMC perspective, these elements function as shared KEY RESOURCES and also as CHANNELS through which the collective reaches different audiences. The collective is formally organized as an “economic association”, a legal persona which is formed to foster the members' economic interest and to run economic activities. The members pay a fee to become and remain members yearly. It is important here that the membership is not cultural, in the sense of sharing ideals or cultural goals with this association, but rather economic, in the sense of being based on using shared resources and finding common ways to sustain each other's crafts.

Not Quite's economic model is, thus, based on revenues from membership fees, share activities like exhibitions and festivals and rent for using workshops and commercial spaces, which together constitute its main REVENUE STREAMS. It offers to the local artists and craft makers the possibility of sharing workshops (and their costs) – which, for many, makes a significant difference in their possibility to start a craft career and stay in the area after their studies or even move to this area – and of marketing themselves within the collective public activities. In this sense, Not Quite articulates a collective VALUE PROPOSITION directed at different CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, including local craft practitioners, visitors, and cultural audiences. What is being proposed here is not only access to workshops or visibility through collective activities, but a broader MULTI-VALUE configuration in which economic support, shared infrastructure, legitimacy, cultural recognition, and the possibility of remaining in the area are held together.

As our research shows, many craft makers find it challenging to sell their work and successfully market themselves individually. In Fengersfors, the collective entrepreneurship of Not Quite represent a significant support for this not only because it attracts customers and tourists, but also because it has come to represent a recognized legitimacy marker in cultural grants application. This is particularly important for young craft makers and for group initiatives. Here, the collective operates as both a CHANNEL and a form of shared

CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP, mediating access to markets and audiences. At the same time, the relevant audience is not exhausted by a broad CUSTOMER SEGMENT. The collective also depends on a more specific HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER: visitors, grant bodies, cultural audiences and local supporters able to value the shared framework of craft production and not only the individual object for sale.

Not Quite has also been important to develop the spirit of collective entrepreneurship that characterizes this ecosystem. This is visible in a number of other more recent initiatives two of which we would like to highlight here before we analyze the common features of this kind of entrepreneurship and what it means for craft. One of these initiatives is the co-working space for artists and craft makers Studio Växt in Dals Långed. Studio Växt was initiated by former students and offers a co-working space for creatives, more recently also ateliers and foster collaboration and innovation. It is also organized as an “economic association” with a membership fee that translates into having a working space in the Studio. Like in the case of Not Quite, each member of the Studio is an independent entrepreneur, but the sharing of resources and the ability of doing projects together support significantly their entrepreneurship. An important activity of the Studio has been to initiate and organize the so-called Byafest every September since 2023. This is a festive event for and with the local inhabitants of the town Dals Långed that brings together the local community around cultural and social activities. Such events function as CHANNELS through which the initiatives reach broader CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, including also local residents and visitors. A SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension is thus visible here, though lightly. Events such as Byafest do not only create visibility for existing practices, but help shape the local social relation to craft by making collective cultural activity part of the life of the town.

A third hub where we have seen the spirit of collective entrepreneurship manifesting and forming during the project is the so-called Open Wood (Figure 9) at the abandoned paper factory Långedsverken. This former industrial premises have been the center of two Interreg European projects fostering design-driven projects focused on wood for sustainable and circular furniture production and experimentations with new technologies. A consistent machine park was acquired by the local regional development organization Mötesplats Steneby and used in Långedsverken, thus constituting an important KEY RESOURCE. Quite soon after the acquisition of the machine and, especially after the end of the first project in 2023, questions arose about what to do with the machines and about possibilities for local craft makers to use them. Picking up on these desires, capabilities and technological assets, the idea from local craft makers has been to organize an open workshop around these machines. HEPHAESTUS has followed and partly accompanied a process of exploring how these machines, many of which are advanced and expensive for individual craft makers, can be commoned in a sustainable way both economically and culturally. This points to an emerging configuration of what we can call collective KEY ACTIVITIES and KEY PARTNERSHIPS, and thus, to another instance of collective entrepreneurship in the making. A first TENSION is already visible here, because shared machinery may become a decisive KEY RESOURCE without there yet being stable or agreed forms of maintenance, access, ownership, and long-term responsibility.

These instances of collective entrepreneurship in the Dals Långed Fengersfors ecosystem show the value of collectivity, community, relations to make craft sustainable and in some cases even doable. Taking the advantage of relatively inexpensive real estate and of the important industrial heritage of this area, craft makers and artists through their collective entrepreneurship have constituted a critical mass of competence that has transformed the towns of Dals Långed and Fengersfors and created a force of attraction for both incoming art and craft students and professional craft makers and artists and increasingly tourists; which thus expands the relevant CUSTOMER SEGMENTS.

Our analysis points at two important learnings from the study of collective entrepreneurship. The first is that the role of institutions in fostering and nurturing entrepreneurship is crucial both indirectly and directly (see Mazzucato, 2018). It is the presence and the active involvement of higher education institutions in the local community that foster a certain kind of entrepreneurship, develop craft competences, and promote a type of contemporary artistic work oriented towards sustainability. These institutions function as KEY PARTNERSHIPS and providers of KEY RESOURCES. It is also the ability to gain and run important European projects that leave traces – material and cultural – on the territory and create the conditions for collective craft entrepreneurship to develop and take care of what the project has created and left at its end.

The second important learning is that this type of collective entrepreneurship shapes a place significantly. This is where PLACE-MAKING becomes especially important. While craft literature often insists on the importance of craft for a place, we would like to emphasize here that this type of entrepreneurship creates craft-based places rather than merely place-based crafts (Duxbury et al., 2025). Of course, the craft is also intimately related to the place and depends on it, but the surprising value of collectivity that we want to stress here is that the place becomes also dependent on craft culturally, economically and organizationally and projects itself into a sort of craftopia. Meaning that the ecosystem can be understood as an evolving configuration which connects VALUE PROPOSITIONS and CUSTOMER SEGMENTS with shared KEY RESOURCES, collective KEY ACTIVITIES and hybrid REVENUE STREAMS.

The first TENSION that arises in this is already mentioned above and concerns shared resources. Workshops, machine parks and other collective KEY RESOURCES can become decisive for the viability of many craft practices without there yet being stable or agreed forms of access, maintenance, ownership, and long-term responsibility. The more central such shared resources become, the more pressing the question of governance becomes as well.

A second TENSION concerns the collective structure of value creation itself. The collectively produced VALUE PROPOSITION, based on shared visibility, infrastructure and mutual support, does not always translate into stable individual REVENUE STREAMS. The collective can create legitimacy, reduce costs and widen audiences, but individual makers still have to sustain their own practices economically.

A third TENSION appears between strong local embeddedness and an increasing orientation toward external CUSTOMER SEGMENTS. The ecosystem is strongly rooted in

place, industrial heritage, and local cooperation, yet it is also increasingly oriented toward visitors, tourists, grant structures, students, and broader cultural networks. Local grounding and external visibility do not automatically reinforce one another.

The questions that follow remain close to these tensions:

- ★ In collectives of craft entrepreneurship, how is individual economic sustainability supported?
- ★ How can resources (e.g. machinery, tools etc.) be repurposed to be shared and commoned in craft communities?
- ★ How can the ecosystem balance and preserve its local identity with growing external visibility?
- ★ What forms of governance and responsibility are needed when shared KEY RESOURCES become central to the viability of many independent craft practices?

Figure 9 - Workshop at Open Wood in Dals Långed; Photo taken by authors in 2025

6.4 Context of Bassano del Grappa and Nove

Bassano del Grappa and Nove are Northern-Italian localities known for their long-lasting relation with artisanal craft practices, which are inextricably woven into the socio-cultural fabric of the region. In particular, ceramic production has played a role for the cultural history of the region but equally in its industrial history. Since the 17th century, the ceramic industry has evolved throughout the region, also with the support of local governments and policy makers. The expansion of the industry has allowed for the formation of different family businesses, most of which have been passed on from one generation to the other, each specialized in different aspect of the ceramic production: from the preparation and supply of the materials to the direct engagement with the material throughout artifacts production.

Ceramics represents today one of the threads linking territory, identity, culture and heritage in the region. They are both a source of pride because of the cultural and symbolic capital the heritage enacts, but also a means through which the territory and its nature reinforce both citizenship and a sense of belonging. The richness of the soil alongside the Brenta River provides raw materials for ceramic production. At the same time, compared with its industrial past, the present craft sector in Bassano del Grappa and Nove displays a much more varied landscape of practices, strategies and organizational forms. That diversity brings into view tensions between innovation and tradition, identity and novelty, and between activities not primarily organized by contemporary economic rationales and the market logics with which they nevertheless have to contend.

While the return to craft has been described as a broader movement of re-enchantment practice (Suddaby et al., 2017), the craft organizations, often configured as SMEs, operate at the intersection of diverse interconnected systems. Shifting between the blurred boundaries of art, design and craft (Shiner, 2012), makers in the region work through different CHANNELS and CUSTOMER SEGMENTS while also responding to the business logics of galleries, exhibition spaces, collectors and other intermediaries. Tensions arise as they renegotiate the economic sustainability of their work, the scale and impact of production and consumption, the need for support infrastructures, and the socio-cultural and symbolic capital they mobilize, enhance and are often expected to preserve and revitalize at the same time.

The following three cases from Bassano del Grappa and Nove approach this regional craft ecosystem through businesses and practices that are closely tied to ceramics (Figure 10), yet differently configured in relation to heritage, artistic identity, materials, channels and viability. Read through our stretched use of the Business Model Canvas, they bring out not only familiar business-model categories, but also a set of pressures that standard business language does not fully resolve.

Figure 10 - Craft Workshops in Bassano del Grappa; Photo taken by authors in 2026

6.4.1 Alberto Scodro

Alberto Scodro is an Italian artist based in the Nove and Bassano del Grappa region, whose practice centers on the creation of unique sculptural works that merge traditional ceramic craftsmanship with experimental material processes. Deeply involved in every stage of production, Alberto Scodro's work emphasizes tactility, form and the expressive qualities of handmade processes, enacted in art pieces that the artists conceive as embodiments of storytelling, cultural heritage and ecological consciousness. Represented by galleries in Belgium, Italy, and Australia, he relies on exhibitions as primary channels for reaching international audiences and buyers, while also using Instagram as a supplementary platform. Although he occasionally collaborates with commercial brands to sustain himself financially, Alberto Scodro's core orientation remains tied to artistic integrity, local heritage and the wish to develop his ceramic practice on its own terms rather than through a business logic centered primarily on revenue or growth.

If approached through the BMC, Alberto Scodro's VALUE PROPOSITION can initially be framed within a recognizable niche-market logic: unique sculptural works are produced and sold through galleries to collectors and cultural institutions. This is not false, but it is too thin. The value of the work does not lie only in scarcity, exclusivity or symbolic distinction in an art market, but just as much in the material and narrative configuration of the pieces themselves.

At the core of his practice lies intrinsic value (Pauls, 1990), since each piece is irreproducible and shaped through material experimentation and a transformative melting process, which is entirely left to the interactions between the materials and the heat of the kiln. From sourcing local stones from the Brenta River and recycled industrial waste to overseeing high-temperature kiln reactions, Scodro preserves unpredictable movements and shifts of the materials as an ontological condition. The work is therefore not simply designed and executed toward a fully controlled end. It is organized so that material transformation,

unpredictability, and the agency of kiln, heat and matter remain integral to the finished object.

This gives the VALUE PROPOSITION a strongly incrustated form. Alberto Scodro's sculptures are offered as singular art objects, but the value they carry is also narrative and territorial. His work shows this territorial embeddedness since it is materially integrated. Locality becomes an inextricable thread tied to form and meaning. Through storytelling, he situates each piece within an ecosystem of materials, heritage, and processes. Value thus emerges as intrinsic, narrative, and symbolic, intersecting with but not reducible to its market circulation. A MULTI-VALUE logic is therefore at work here, though in a version shaped less by service or experiential participation than by the relation between material process, place and the singular object.

This also sharpens the place of the HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER. The relevant audience is not simply anyone willing to buy sculptures. The work depends on collectors, galleries and viewers who can respond to scarcity, aesthetic distinction, and symbolic value, but also to the material and territorial story carried by the object. The customer hoped for is therefore narrower than an ordinary CUSTOMER SEGMENT and more strongly tied to a willingness to value singularity, process and embeddedness together, or a readiness to engage in this kind of evaluation.

Several tensions follow from this. A first TENSION lies in the relation between intrinsic value and business-model language, and it raises important questions such as: Can intrinsic value be articulated within a framework oriented primarily toward value capture? Can local embeddedness and narrative articulation be adequately contained and communicated effectively? And can a practice such as Alberto Scodro's be reframed into a value-ecology, where intrinsic, symbolic and economic dimensions coexist without being subordinated to a single metric? These questions matter because the work does not merely add cultural or ecological value to an otherwise ordinary product. The object is constituted through those dimensions from the outset.

The same pressure appears when one turns from VALUE PROPOSITION toward KEY RESOURCES, KEY ACTIVITIES, CHANNELS and CUSTOMER SEGMENTS. As indicated, several sets of resources are mobilized by Alberto Scodro throughout the different activities that compose its practice. Local stones from the river Brenta, recycled waste, clay, and mineral compounds represent the material resources that co-participate in the design and formation of the final art pieces. The material production of the pieces is subdivided into experimental assemblage, testing of chemical reactions, firing, heating, and ongoing adjustment to processes that are never fully reducible to control.

That is one reason PLACE-MAKING matters here. Nove and the Brenta River are not merely background to Alberto Scodro's practice. Local stone, ceramic heritage and regional material memory enter directly into the work and help shape what it can mean. Nove's ceramic heritage thus plays a role in shaping Alberto Scodro's pool of symbolic capital and storytelling, which is renegotiated in the encounter with his own knowledge of materials and artistic sensibility. The work does not only happen in the region but also participates in

sustaining the region as a place where ceramic heritage can still be materially transformed rather than merely represented.

A second TENSION concerns scale and scarcity. Represented by galleries and participating in exhibitions Scodro can articulate and present the storytelling behind his artworks, attracting customers among art collectors, mostly attracted aesthetic and symbolic values, by uniqueness and scarcity. In these terms, prioritization of scaling up does not play a role in Scodro's business model, as an attention to a modest production volume to participate in the perception of value of the customers. Limited production is not an obstacle to be overcome, but part of the condition under which the work can retain its meaning and value. Growth therefore does not appear here as a neutral good. A larger output could undermine the very scarcity and singularity on which both the art-market position and the symbolic force of the work depend.

A third TENSION lies in how the BMC handles the status of materials and processes. From a BMC perspective, Scodro's KEY RESOURCES and KEY ACTIVITIES, as well as customers and channels, can be described with clarity. Yet such categorization risks to obscure the relational and cultural dimensions that sustain his work. If stones, kiln heat, and chemical reactions actively co-shape the outcome, can they remain mere "resources," or do they approach the status of silent partners? Can embodied expertise and generational craft knowledge be adequately captured and communicated? Can a framework be oriented toward strategic optimization represent a practice in which scarcity, limited production, and institutional negotiation are conditions of value itself? This is one of the places where standard business-model language begins to strain, because the work depends on relations between object, material, place and process that do not stay neatly inside one category.

What comes under pressure here, then, is not only how the work is sold, but how it can be described at all without flattening what makes it valuable. Alberto Scodro's practice has to hold together singularity and market circulation, ecological embeddedness and symbolic distinction, locality and international exhibition, modest volume and financial viability. Those are not external complications added to an otherwise stable business. They belong to the form the practice takes.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ How can intrinsic value be articulated within a framework oriented primarily toward value capture?
- ★ How can ecological embeddedness and narrative articulation be communicated without reducing them to secondary features?
- ★ If local stones, kiln heat, chemical reactions, and unpredictability actively shape the work, should they be understood only as KEY RESOURCES, or as conditions of value that exceed that category?
- ★ When scarcity and limited production are part of what gives the work value, what kind of growth remains possible and on what terms?

6.4.2 Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa

Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa are ceramic artisans based in Nove, Italy, where they operate a multifaceted organized business practice rooted in the town's long-standing ceramic tradition (see Figure 11). Elena, a third-generation ceramicist, leads the creative direction of their work, while Bruno contributes with technical expertise, together forming a collaborative partnership that bridges artistic experimentation and craft precision. Their practice spans several interconnected key activities and encompasses both service- and product-oriented: ceramic production through the family workshop Sartori Ceramiche, design and consulting projects through their studio TERA, and teaching engagements, notably at ISIA Roma Design. Rather than pursuing mass production, they focus on limited series and unique pieces that merge art and craft, emphasizing cultural heritage, sustainability and high-quality craftsmanship. Their work is also marked by a sustained effort to preserve and renew Nove's ceramic tradition while cultivating relationships with clients who value the artistic, cultural and environmental dimensions embedded in what they make.

The VALUE PROPOSITION is therefore not centered on one clearly separable offer. Ceramic objects remain central, but the practice is organized across production, design collaboration and teaching, and these activities do not simply sit beside one another as independent lines of work. They help define each other. Elena and Bruno's value proposition is not constructed around a single product or a clear offering, but rather around an assemblage of practices that interlace craft production, design collaboration and teaching. Their ceramic artefacts embody technical and material expertise, but they also carry forward a lineage of tacit knowledge, family trade and local industrial heritage. Teaching matters here for the same reason. It does not function only as financial stabilization, but as part of the reproduction and renewal of the ecosystem from which the practice emerges. Consultancy and collaboration extend that same configuration rather than standing outside it.

That is why the work has to be understood through a MULTI-VALUE logic. Economic value remains necessary, but it is bound up with heritage, technical excellence, continuity, pedagogy and the wish to maintain autonomy rather than maximize scale. Value is distributed across objects, relations, teaching and longer-term continuity. This also makes the HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER more specific than a broad CUSTOMER SEGMENT would suggest. Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa do not simply depend on anyone willing to buy ceramic objects or services. The practice depends on people willing to respond to the work as something carrying artistic development, technical precision, generational continuity and local heritage together.

A first TENSION appears here. This multiplicity raises structural questions when confronted with the business model canvas. Can a single value proposition capture a practice that oscillates between artist, designer, craft maker and teacher? Does generational continuity constitute a form of value – and if so, where does it reside within the canvas? The difficulty is not that the practice lacks a value proposition, but that it cannot be reduced without loss to one dominant expression of value. What has to be held together is not one offer with a few extensions, but an ecology of activities and identities that together sustain the work.

The same density appears in the relation between KEY RESOURCES and KEY ACTIVITIES. Elena and Bruno's practice mobilizes diverse key resources and activities which are inseparable from their territorial and generational embeddedness. Their technical expertise, developed through long-term engagement with ceramic materials and reinforced by Elena's position as a third-generation maker, constitutes a central embodied resource. That expertise is supported by Nove's industrial territory, whose infrastructure and knowledge networks make both small-scale artisanal production and collaboration with design companies possible. Material sourcing remains largely local, reinforcing the continuity between heritage and contemporary production. Alongside craft production, consultancy and collaboration form a relevant part of the work, while teaching introduces another dimension that is geographically more dispersed but still central to the identity and reproduction of the practice.

This is one of the places where TEMPORAL NAVIGATION matters. The difficulty lies not simply in having too much to do, but in having to sustain one practice across different temporal demands that do not follow the same rhythm. Production, teaching, collaboration and travel each claim time differently and each matter differently to the continuity of the work. Teaching, for example, contributes to income, identity and knowledge transmission at once. It cannot be treated as a detachable side activity without changing the configuration of the practice itself.

PLACE-MAKING matters just as strongly. Nove is not merely where Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa happen to work. The family workshop, the local sourcing, the industrial territory, and the inherited relation to ceramic production all enter directly into the meaning and distinctiveness of the practice. Their work does not only take place in Nove, but also helps sustain Nove as a place where ceramic tradition continues through present activity rather than through heritage discourse alone.

A second TENSION follows from this. The practice is strengthened by its multiplicity, yet that same multiplicity makes it difficult to present a single clear business core. When framed through the BMC, these elements can be framed across key resources, key activities, customer segments, and revenue streams. Nevertheless, such categorization partly obscures the layers that structure their organization. Teaching, for instance, functions simultaneously as revenue stream, knowledge reproduction, and identity formation. Generational expertise operates both as KEY RESOURCE and as part of what is being valued in the work itself. Time allocation between production and education shapes not only operational capacity, but the very form of the enterprise.

That is also why the business model building blocks begin to strain here. Its static framework does not capture entirely these temporal negotiations, in which artistic autonomy, economic sustainability, and intergenerational continuity are constantly negotiated. Rather than presenting a clear "core business," Elena and Bruno's configuration appears as an iterative negotiation between overlapping roles and commitments. The problem is not that the business model canvas says nothing, but that it separates too neatly what this practice keeps in motion together.

A SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimension is also clearly present. Teaching and consultancy do not simply extend the sale of objects into adjacent services. They help reproduce a field of ceramic knowledge, standards and judgment that exceeds any single artefact. In that sense, the practice participates not only in making and selling ceramics, but in maintaining the conditions under which ceramic tradition can still be learned and renewed. What has to be held together here is a dense relation between heritage and experimentation, product and service, teaching and production, local continuity and broader design networks, and artistic autonomy and economic sustainability. Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa’s practice exists through the continual negotiation of those relations rather than through their simplification.

The questions that follow should therefore remain close to these tensions:

- ★ Can a single value proposition capture a practice that moves between artist, designer, craft maker and teacher?
- ★ How should teaching be understood within the business model when it functions at once as revenue stream, knowledge reproduction and identity formation?
- ★ When generational continuity, territorial embeddedness and technical expertise all matter, where do they belong in the BMC: as KEY RESOURCES, as part of the VALUE PROPOSITION, or as both?
- ★ How can temporal negotiations between production, teaching, collaboration and longer-term continuity be made more visible within the business model?

Figure 11 - Students from CBS visiting workshop of Elena Rausse & Bruno Testa in Nove; Photo taken by authors in 2024

6.4.3 Cuko Ceramics

Cuko Ceramics is a small-scale ceramic enterprise based in Nove, Italy, founded and managed by Serena Reginato and Giulia Cominato. The company produces handmade ceramic sex toys that combine the town's long-standing ceramic traditions with contemporary, avant-garde design. Positioned as an alternative to conventional silicone-based products, Cuko emphasizes both sustainability and sensual exploration, promoting what they describe as slow sex: a way of approaching intimacy that foregrounds attention, duration, and bodily awareness rather than speed, disposability, or standardized use. Their production remains locally anchored, relying on regional materials and collaborators in order to preserve craft knowledge and support the local ceramic community. Beyond selling products, Cuko seeks to create social, cultural, and ecological value by challenging dominant sexual norms, addressing issues such as allergy-friendly materials and sexual education, and integrating environmental consciousness into their business model within the broader context of the Anthropocene (Figure 12).

If confronted with a BMC, the configuration of Cuko's production underlines aspirations that cannot easily be encapsulated within a predetermined framework. Looking first at VALUE PROPOSITION in its most conventional sense, the product seems to fit a recognizable problem-solution articulation. The problem was, in fact, identified, within the social sphere inhabited by the artisans, in the allergy to silicone and the discomfort caused by it. Shifting material provided a direct solution to the problem. A second bodily problem also enters the proposition through endometriosis, since the form and material of the ceramic object make possible a gentler and more careful alternative to many other products in the same category. And yet that is only the most immediate legible level of the proposition. By maintaining production in Nove and collaborating with local suppliers, the enterprise contributes to preserving and revitalizing a ceramic tradition that has been in decline. The object is therefore not only an alternative to silicone, but tied to a local material history, to the continuity of ceramic knowledge in Nove, and to a deliberate attempt to keep that heritage active by redirecting it into a new field of use. The proposition is not merely functional, but also territorial and cultural.

A further layer appears in the way Giulia and Serena frame the work as a cultural and educational intervention. The design and production of ceramic-based sex toys is, moreover, configured as a cultural and educational intervention in the ecosystem, challenging the "fast-sex" mentality, which is shaped by pornography, heteronormativity, and insufficient sexual education (Gancitano, 2024), and a culturally conservative environment for which sex discourses remains taboo. The object is therefore asked to do more than solve discomfort. It also intervenes in a field of norms, habits, silences, and expectations. In that sense, the proposition cannot be understood only in terms of use-value. It also seeks to reshape what can be said, taught, and explored around intimacy, craft, and embodied experience.

The ecological layer does not stand outside these others. At last, Giulia and Serena's product let them reflect upon environmental and climate discourses around the sustainability

and impact of their work. On one side the consciousness of producing a more durable and less materially impactful object emerges in the campaign “sustainably spicy”, while on the others the sustainability of the production is constantly renegotiated by reflecting on the environmental costs of powering the kilns and extract materials, despite the scale at which they operate: careful consideration is iteratively raised upon sustainable choices and greenwashing behaviours avoidance. What matters here is that sustainability does not enter as a solved attribute. It remains a pressure internal to the practice. The object may be more durable and materially careful than many alternatives, yet the work still depends on kilns, extraction, transport, and other costly processes. Ecological value is present, but so is ecological difficulty.

This is why the proposition does not remain singular for long. Hence, the ceramic sex toy appears at first defined, the value proposition informed by a clearly outlined problem. And yet the value that is created and delivered by Cuko Ceramics is configured throughout multiple instances: alternative to silicone-based products; gentle response to endometriosis; embodying localized craft knowledge of Nove (cultural value); social and educational purposes (social value); sustainably spicy and environmental consciousness (ecological value). What begins as a relatively clear problem-solution articulation quickly expands into something more layered. A MULTI-VALUE logic organized the business from within. Economic value remains necessary, but the object also carries bodily, cultural, educational, ecological, and place-based value at the same time. Thus, Cuko’s product is clear enough when introduced as a ceramic alternative to silicone. But that is only one part of what it proposes. The same object also carries local craft knowledge, educational intent, and environmental reflection. If the proposition is stated only in functional terms, too much disappears. If all dimensions are stated at once, it risks becoming blurred. The tension lies precisely here: how to articulate a value proposition that is plural without collapsing into vagueness.

The same difficulty appears again once one moves beyond VALUE PROPOSITION and looks at the wider business configuration through which that proposition is sustained in practice. Throughout the production, Cuko Ceramics mobilizes different sets of resources: locally sourced materials, the ceramic heritage of Nove, and local production networks. The complementary skills and competencies of Giulia and Serena matter just as much here. Giulia’s craft expertise and Serena’s marketing and communication abilities make possible not only material production and sales, but also the broader framing through which the object becomes intelligible as something more than a functional substitute.

This also affects how KEY ACTIVITIES should be understood. Production remains central, but the enterprise does not depend on production alone. It also depends on communication, explanation, and participation in cultural networks. Marketing is therefore important not only because it promotes the object, but because it places it within narratives of intimacy, responsibility, locality, and craft continuity. What the business does is not exhausted by making ceramic sex toys. It also has to make clear why these objects should be valued not only as functional substitutes, but as carriers of locality, craft continuity, bodily care and a different way of approaching intimacy.

This, in turn, sharpens the question of the HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER. Communication and educational intent are directed towards anticipated or potentially existing customers that are individuals open to reflection and sensory exploration and who value education and durability over convenience and disposability. The enterprise does not seem to depend only on people seeking a substitute product. It depends on people willing to respond to the object at a fuller level: as something involving bodily care, reflection, locality, durability, and a different tempo of intimacy.

Something SOCIALLY FORMATIVE is therefore at stake here. The product does not remain a passive commodity. It helps make other conversations possible around intimacy, materiality, sexuality, and care. In this sense, Cuko does not only answer an existing demand, but also helps shape the terms in which that demand is understood. EDUCATIONABILITY matters directly here because part of the proposition depends on a customer willing to learn to value the object differently: not only as a functional item, but as something carrying craft knowledge, durability, locality, and a different relation to bodily use.

PLACE-MAKING is equally central. Throughout the production, Cuko Ceramics mobilizes different sets of resources: locally sourced materials, the ceramic heritage of Nove, and local production networks. The enterprise did not simply choose Nove as a convenient production site. Ceramic heritage, local materials, and production networks do not merely support the business from outside. They enter the proposition itself. This kind of relationship between the locality, the resources, and the configuration of Cuko Ceramics' activities is generative of normative commitments regarding the possibilities of scaling up production: the ceramic sex-toy is embedded in Nove the same way Nove is embedded in the craft artefacts. That relationship immediately introduces another TENSION, namely between embeddedness and scale. Hence, despite material possibilities and opportunities to expand the reach and output of their activities, Giulia and Serena's consciously adopt a stasis- or degrowth-oriented approach (Rennstam & Paulsson, 2024; Nesterova & Buch-Hansen, 2023) to the definition of their own business, prioritizing community resilience, durable products, and short supply chains over expansion and profit maximization. Growth is therefore not simply a desirable horizon deferred for practical reasons. It is itself under question, because the conditions that make the work meaningful are also those most likely to come under pressure from ordinary scaling logics.

From a BMC perspective, CUSTOMER SEGMENT, KEY ACTIVITIES, and KEY RESOURCES can still be named. At the same time, the model risks to overlook and limit the interplay between the components that contribute to shape and configure Cuko Ceramics' organization and practice. The issue is not that the BMC says nothing. It is that it tends to separate what, in this case, is most active in combination.

This becomes especially clear in the way locality and materiality behave. The locality, together with its cultural heritage and ceramic tradition represents a key resource, and at the same time is allowed to exercise agency on business' design processes. The material, vehicle of symbolic and cultural values, and keep its own agency once it is transformed in the final artefacts, from being a resource it participates silently to the educational communication and place-making efforts in the long-term, making it almost resemble a key partner, beyond being a resource. What comes under pressure here is not only the

adequacy of one block in the canvas, but the separation between blocks themselves. With Cuko, resource, partner, proposition and place do not stay neatly apart.

That is why the BMC appears here less as a false tool than as an insufficiently elastic one. The BMC risks reducing the enterprise to a simplified economic schema and overlooking the complex interplay of care, locality, and sustainability that sustains it, but how can it be stretched to frame the fluidity and interplay of the components that sustains and are produced by the craft organization? Also in this case, the question is not whether business-model language should be abandoned, but whether it can be used in a way that remains attentive to overlap, non-human participation and value negotiations that do not end in price alone. It can be used exactly in terms of its limitations.

What comes into view, then, is a business that must hold together several difficult relations at once: between problem-solution clarity and value plurality, between VALUE PROPOSITION and the wider configuration of KEY RESOURCES and KEY ACTIVITIES that sustain it, between locality and growth, between ecological aspiration and ecological cost, between commercial communication and educational communication, and between the separable blocks of the BMC and the more fluid ecology through which the enterprise actually operates. These tensions are not incidental to Cuko Ceramics but belong to the way it exists as a craft business at all.

The questions that follow therefore remain close to these pressures:

- ★ How can you communicate your value proposition clearly if it entails multiple values at the same time (MULTI VALUE)?
- ★ How is care and other non-monetary aspects accounted as core aspects of my practice?
- ★ How can you account for environmental and sustainable aspects of your craft practices?
- ★ How can non-human actors be included effectively in your business model?
- ★ How can degrowth be communicated through your business model as part of storytelling?

Figure 12 - Poster created by students from CBS in Venice in 2024 during fieldwork, displaying Cuko Ceramics Business Model

7.0 From EMERGENT CATEGORIES to PRISMS in relation to the BMC

The case analyses have made a number of recurring pressures and TENSIONS visible across the Bornholm, Venice, Bassano del Grappa and Nove, and Dals Långed and Fengersfors ecosystems. Some of these were already approached through the earlier analytical categories, above all CRAFT VALUE PROPOSITION and HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER. Others became clearer only through the movement from case to case, where MULTI-VALUE in practice, SOCIALLY FORMATIVE dimensions, EDUCATIONABILITY,

PLACE-MAKING, TEMPORAL NAVIGATION, and the shifting relation between person, practice and business emerged as broader results of the analyses themselves. These are not new starting categories placed on top of the material, but what the cases have gradually made clear is necessary to take into account across one another.

What follows takes those results one step further by reading them as PRISMS in relation to the BMC. The purpose is to help the reader see more clearly what the standard BMC can still describe well, what it captures only partially, and where its categories need to be read more reflectively in relation to craft. A prism, in this sense, gathers a recurrent pressure and brings it back to the language of VALUE PROPOSITION, CUSTOMER SEGMENT, CHANNEL, KEY RESOURCES, KEY ACTIVITIES, PARTNERSHIPS, and viability. The point is not to propose a new craft canvas or a replacement set of building blocks. It is to show why the existing vocabulary remains useful and why it also begins to thin out the practices it is meant to describe when value, responsiveness, time, place, limits and maintenance become decisive.

Moreover, the prisms directly relate to and inspire the TOOLKIT for business models in craft (see Appendix C). The toolkit is one result of the analyses of the cases, the BMC building blocks and the emerging categories and themes. It aims to turn these broader analytical results into a flexible set of reflections, points of orientation and questions. In this way, it may help craft makers engage more reflectively with their own practices and with the conditions shaping them. The toolkit grows out of the analyses as their more directly usable outcome. Its purpose is not to offer a fixed model for every craft business, but to make recurrent tensions, variables and possibilities more visible and more workable in particular situations.

The first prisms already indicate what this shift makes possible. #1 NEGOTIATING TIME gathers the recurring difficulty that appears where making, experimentation, teaching, workshops, administration, recovery and longer development cannot be brought under one rhythm or one measure of viability. #2 MAKING PLACE gathers another, where locality enters the proposition, the continuity of skill, the organization of shared resources and the limits within which a practice can remain itself. #3 GROWTH, LIMITS AND MAINTENANCE, #4 FORMING RESPONSIVENESS, and #5 CONDENSED VALUE continue that same movement. These prisms do not leave the cases behind, but allow the reader to return to them with a sharper sense of what they have been showing all along, and with a clearer view of how craft business both fits and stretches the descriptive language of the BMC.

#1 NEGOTIATING TIME — Across the cases, time becomes difficult wherever craft practices depend on activities that move according to different rhythms and matter in different ways. Production has one tempo, while experimentation has another. Teaching, workshops, customer relation, administration, travel, recovery and longer development all make their own claims. NEGOTIATING TIME names the condition in which a practice remains viable only by negotiating among these competing temporal demands, without being able to reduce them to one common measure or a single way of organizing them.

This becomes visible in different forms across the cases. In the Bornholm ecosystem, practices such as Christina Schou's have to hold together making, experimentation,

teaching, workshops and development within one finite working life, which is also why the pressure of overcommitment enters so early into the organization of the practice. In the Venice context, the issue often appears as a friction between the slower time required by craft processes and the shorter time imposed by tourism, temporary presence and accelerated attention. In Bassano and Nove, it appears where production, teaching, consultancy and continuity all remain necessary while following different schedules and different horizons of importance. In Baltic Sea Glass, the same pressure even becomes bodily: recovery, pacing and the preservation of skill are not secondary concerns, but conditions of the work itself. Hence, questions of sustainable pace and the health of the maker already belong to the practice from within. What recurs across these different settings is the difficulty of keeping a practice coherent when the times it depends on pull in different directions.

NEGOTIATING TIME therefore points to more than workload. It concerns the way value, purpose and endurance are distributed across time. Some activities bring income more directly, some sustain identity, some preserve quality, some build future capability, and some protect the bodily and relational conditions without which the work cannot continue. Once this becomes visible, time can no longer be treated as a neutral resource to be allocated efficiently. It becomes one of the places where the deeper order of the practice is tested. The co-dependency between cost of time and the visibility of time make them almost impossible to treat as secondary managerial matters.

What this prism makes visible is that time in craft business is constantly arranged, defended and weighed, and that the practice holds together only as long as that work succeeds. For a craft business, NEGOTIATING TIME is a constant effort of mediation between oneself, one's practice and surrounding conditions.

#2 MAKING PLACE — As shown throughout the case accounts above, place becomes active in craft business where materials, skills, workshops, institutions and local forms of continuity enter directly into what the work is and what it can become. What is being sustained is often not only a PRODUCT, a SERVICE, a shared EXPERIENCE, diverse lines of production, or various combinations of these elements, but a relation to locality that gives the practice force, recognizability and intelligibility. As a prism, MAKING PLACE names the way locality enters the practice itself and helps sustain the conditions under which that practice can continue to carry meaning.

The ecosystem of Dals Långed and Fengersfors make this especially clear. Not Quite, Studio Växt and the developing Open Wood initiative show how shared workshops, reused industrial buildings, local institutions and commoned resources help hold together an environment in which craft remains livable and developable. What matters here is the practical work through which collective organization, shared infrastructures and local commitment make it possible to stay, work and develop there. Through that work, Dals Långed and Fengersfors are sustained as a place for and by craft. Read through the BMC, this places pressure on any simple separation between KEY RESOURCES, KEY PARTNERSHIPS and the wider environment of the business, since locality here is not a neutral setting but part of what the practice itself helps sustain. Shared resources are therefore not a secondary issue here, as they belong to the way locality is made workable,

and so too does the question of how a place can gain external visibility without losing the conditions that hold it together.

One side of this prism concerns the way locality enters the value proposition through material conditions and inherited ways of making. In the practice of Christina Schou, this becomes visible where granite, circular experimentation and the relation to the Bornholm craft ecology belong to the work itself. In the work of Cuko Ceramics, local ceramic knowledge, production in the Nove territory and the wish to keep that knowledge active are bound into the object from the beginning. Here, locality does not appear as a symbolic addition attached after the fact. It helps determine what can be made and why it matters in the way it does. At this point the BMC can still name VALUE PROPOSITION and KEY RESOURCES, but only partially, because what is being proposed already includes a place-bound form of meaning that cannot easily be detached from the material and inherited conditions of making. Here, place-based authenticity appears in a stronger sense than branding can capture, since locality is carried inside the proposition itself.

Another side of the prism of making places like this concerns the way locality enters the value proposition through material conditions and inherited ways of making. In the practice of Christina Schou, this becomes visible where granite, circular experimentation and the relation to the Bornholm craft ecology belong to the work itself. In the work of Cuko Ceramics, local ceramic knowledge, production in the Nove territory and the wish to keep that knowledge active are bound into the object from the beginning. Here, locality does not appear as a symbolic addition attached after the fact. It helps determine what can be made and why it matters in the way it does. At this point the BMC can still name VALUE PROPOSITION and KEY RESOURCES, but it does so only partially, because what is being proposed already includes a place-bound form of meaning that cannot easily be detached from the material and inherited conditions of making. Here a place-based kind of authenticity clearly appears in a stronger sense than can be referred to with branding, since locality is carried inside the proposition itself.

Another side of the prism concerns continuity. This becomes visible in the work of Baltic Sea Glass, where workshop, coastal setting and the continuity of glassmaking shape how the objects are encountered and valued. It is equally visible in the work of Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa, where the workshop, the generational history, the district and inherited technical culture remain active within present work. Continuity here depends on being enacted in the presence of this work, and it lasts only where inherited forms, skills and relations remain active within the practice. The BMC has difficulty registering this kind of continuity clearly, because it can appear at once as KEY RESOURCE, as part of the VALUE PROPOSITION, and as one of the conditions under which the practice remains recognizable to itself and to others. The continued use of forms, skills and relations is what allows a local identity to remain active within the practice rather than receding into image or memory.

Yet another side of the prism appears where locality gives force and exposes the practice to pressure at the same time. In Atelier 23 and Atelier Volante, local networks, artisanal continuity and attachment to inherited forms of making give the work much of its significance, while also leaving it exposed to rent pressure, imitation, transient attention and the demand to simplify what is being made so that it can circulate more easily in a tourism economy. A

related pressure appears in the work of Cuko Ceramics and Alberto Scodro, where locality gives density and distinctiveness to the work while also limiting certain forms of substitution, scaling and growth. Place therefore enters not only as value, but as a condition that can be weakened when the work is pulled too far away from the terms that sustain it. Also, here the BMC can identify CHANNELS, CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, RESOURCES and PARTNERSHIPS, but it says less easily how locality may function at once as force, limit and exposure, which is what a business model for craft making would call for. External visibility becomes difficult along exactly this line, because visibility may strengthen recognition while also increasing the pressure to circulate on terms set elsewhere.

The prism of MAKING PLACE concerns the way craft practice contributes to sustaining local worlds in which materials, skills, relations and standards of value can still hold together. Under this prism, locality enters the craft value proposition, the continuity of skill, and the limits within which the practice can remain itself. Local identity, place-based authenticity, external visibility and the preservation of shared resources lie close to the same pressure, not as separate additions to the analysis, but as different ways in which the work of making place becomes legible.

#3 GROWTH, LIMITS AND MAINTENANCE — The prism of GROWTH, LIMITS AND MAINTENANCE gathers a pressure that runs through many of the cases wherever continuation depends less on expansion than on preserving the conditions under which the practice can remain itself. In craft business, viability does not always point toward increased output, broader reach or greater speed. It often depends on limits that have to be kept in place, on forms of care that prevent depletion, and on maintenance work without which the practice would lose the very qualities that make it worth sustaining.

This becomes clear where growth in craft practice is actively refused or held at a distance. In Inkyong Lee's work, increased production would compromise the ethical and perceptual orientation of the work itself. The object depends on restraint, while the practice depends on not allowing demand to dictate its scale. Cuko Ceramics brings out a related pressure, since local production, material commitments and a slower relation to use would all be threatened by forms of expansion that detach the object from the conditions that give it meaning. What appears here is a different and necessary judgment about what growth would cost, not a negation of its existence.

The same pressure returns where continuation depends on maintenance in a more literal sense. In Baltic Sea Glass, the health of the maker, the pacing of work and the continued bodily possibility of glassblowing belong to the survival of the business itself. In the Dals Långed and Fengersfors practices, shared workshops, commoned machinery and collective infrastructures remain viable only through governance, upkeep and practical responsibility distributed across a local environment. In both, maintenance is not secondary to business activity, but one of the forms through which the practice continues at all, making it what it is.

Another side of the tensions of this prism appears where development remains necessary, yet cannot be pursued without drawing on finite time, energy and organizational capacity. Christina Schou's practice shows this through the pressure of keeping experimentation, production, teaching and longer-term material development alive, within one limited working

life. FabLab Venezia gives the same issue a more institutional form, since access, sustainability, and public-oriented capability all depend on keeping a fragile organization operative without turning it toward profit as its primary measure. Here too the question is not simply whether growth occurs, but what has to be maintained, protected or refused for the work to remain coherent.

Read through the BMC, this prism places pressure on any easy alignment between VALUE PROPOSITION, REVENUE STREAMS, KEY ACTIVITIES, and long-term viability. The BMC can still register growth, cost and organizational structure, yet it says less easily how a practice may depend on staying small, protecting pace, refusing certain markets, or maintaining bodies, relations, and shared resources as conditions of survival. Under this prism, growth is only one possible movement of a business. Limits and maintenance belong just as centrally to the question of how a craft practice continues without being thinned out by the very forms of success it is asked to pursue.

#4 FORMING RESPONSIVENESS — The prism of FORMING RESPONSIVENESS gathers a recurring pressure in the analysis above wherever the value proposition of a craft business depends on much more than the presence of demand. What matters in these instances is a more exact kind of reception. A product, a service or a shared experience may be available, recognizable and even saleable, while still failing to become effective in the fuller terms on which the practice depends. The proposition often depends on attention to process, responsiveness to labour, interest in origin, willingness to learn, as well as receptiveness to locality and material meaning. This prism concerns this part of craft business where responsiveness cannot simply be presupposed and therefore has to be formed.

This becomes especially clear where the work depends on a changed relation to the object or to the act of receiving it. That pressure is particularly strong in the practices of Inkyong Lee and Cuko Ceramics, though in different ways. One ties the object to reflection on need, labour and responsibility, while the other asks to be received through bodily care, locality and a slower relation to intimacy. What matters in both is not merely that something is offered, but that the offer depends on another mode of response than ordinary consumption alone.

The same pressure appears where explanation, encounter, and mediation belong to the proposition itself. The work of Baltic Sea Glass, Atelier Volante, and FabLab Venezia all make this visible. In these practices, the value of the work is not exhausted by the object, the tool, or the service taken in isolation. Reception is shaped through storytelling, workshop encounters, explanation, translation, or guided use. In that sense, responsiveness is not external to the business relation but is co-produced through the practice itself.

A further difficulty appears where the qualities central to the work do not declare themselves immediately. This can concern technical precision, generational continuity, place-bound meaning, process, reuse or circular material development, as in the cases of Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa, Atelier 23 and Christina Schou. Here the problem is not simply communication in the narrow sense. It is that the VALUE PROPOSITION depends on the

legibility of qualities that are easily missed unless the practice itself creates conditions for their recognition.

Read through the BMC, this prism places pressure on any simple relation between VALUE PROPOSITION, CUSTOMER SEGMENT, CHANNEL, and CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP. The BMC can still identify these elements, but it says less easily how a business may depend on forming the response it needs from those to whom it is directed. Under this prism, HOPED-FOR CUSTOMER and EDUCATIONABILITY move close together. FORMING RESPONSIVENESS concerns the way craft business works on the possibility of being properly received.

#5 CONDENSED VALUE —The prism of CONDENSED VALUE is supposed to gather a pressure that appears wherever too much of what matters is carried in the same product, service, shared experience or practice for it to be rendered clearly in one register alone. The problem is not vagueness, but rather the density. A VALUE PROPOSITION may be perfectly legible at the level of function or sale and still remain poorly described if cultural continuity, bodily care, locality, ecological commitment, technical skill, symbolic force, as well as material meaning are all active within it at the very same time. Under this prism, value is not simply multiple, as it is held together in forms that are clearly diminished when they are thinned out into one dominant meaning.

This is clear where the object in center carries several orders of value at once. With Cuko Ceramics, the object can be approached as a ceramic alternative to silicone, yet that does not exhaust what is being proposed. Bodily care, local ceramic knowledge, education, durability and ecological reflection all remain active within the same proposition, embedded in the same object. Alberto Scodro's work shows how scarcity and aesthetic distinction matter, but so do local stones, territorial memory, kiln process and ecological embeddedness. Here, value does not sit in one feature among others. It is condensed in the thing itself.

The same density appears where the proposition is spread across several expressions without becoming separable. In Atelier 23, the work carries product, process, locality, collaboration and possible reuse together. In Christina Schou's work, material experimentation, circular reuse, workshop activity, and artistic development are bound into one evolving practice. In Baltic Sea Glass, object, storytelling, workshop encounter and local continuity cannot be pulled apart without reducing what the work is worth. Here value is not attached afterward through narrative or context, but is already present in the way the proposition holds together.

Read through the BMC, this prism places pressure on any simple account of VALUE PROPOSITION and VALUE CAPTURE. The BMC can still name the proposition, the resource base, the activities, and the customer relation, yet it says less easily how several kinds of value may be condensed in the same form without being reducible to one another. Under this prism, craft business often depends on propositions whose force lies precisely in the density with which material, social, cultural, ecological and symbolic value are carried together. That is why this prism lies close to questions of multi-value, intrinsic value, care, ecological embeddedness, and the difficulty of communicating propositions that hold several

kinds of worth at once. CONDENSED VALUE concerns the way craft business carries more than one order of value in the same form, and the difficulty of keeping that density legible without flattening it.

8.0 The integration of Intellectual Property in the toolkit

An additional and important aspect that emerges when working with business models for craft in the HEPHAESTUS ecosystems, is the area of Intellectual Property (IP). As the previous sections show, a substantial share of the value revealed by the case studies lies in the intangible dimensions of craftsmanship. It resides in reputation, authenticity, place-based identity, aesthetic distinctiveness, credibility of heritage-linked knowledge, as well as in community-building. These value dimensions can be central to sustainability, because they enable craft makers to justify fair pricing, resist low-cost imitation, and maintain long-term viability without resorting to high-volume production. IP should therefore be considered part of a toolkit for business models in craft. Not only an important legal add-on to craft business IP also represents a mechanism of value capture and value safeguarding. This is especially true where craft enterprises operate in tourism-driven markets such as Venice, but equally in digital markets where copying is easy and provenance difficult to verify.

Therefore, from a business model perspective, IP can be understood as part of the “infrastructure” that stabilizes a craftmaker’s value proposition over time (Teece, 1986). On the one hand, it can strengthen differentiation by protecting distinctive signs, brands, and design features, thereby reducing risks of unfair competition and reputational dilution in markets where lookalike products circulate quickly (EUIPO, 2022). On the other hand, IP regimes can introduce costs and complexity that disproportionately affect micro- and small enterprises, creating a practical IP tension between the need for protection and the realities of limited time, expertise, and financial resources. This makes IP a relevant dimension of craft business model thinking, as it shapes who benefits from craft value, under what conditions, and with what forms of support (Covarrubia, 2019).

Intellectual property and the creative sector: relevance and current tensions

Intellectual property (IP) plays an important role in supporting Europe’s creative economy, cultural heritage, and innovation capacity (Calabrese, 2024; Bullich, 2020). For artists, craft makers, designers, and small creative businesses, IP can provide tools to protect intangible value, including reputation, originality, product appearance, technical solutions, and place-based identity. Therefore, IP is not only a legal issue, but also a matter of industrial policy, cultural policy, regional development, and competitiveness.

The relevance of IP in this field is increasing. Creative and craft-based products circulate rapidly across digital and cross-border markets, where imitation can be easy and enforcement difficult. At the same time, consumers are placing growing value on

authenticity, origin, sustainability, and local know-how. This makes legal frameworks for protection more significant, particularly where products derive value from design, heritage, or regional reputation (Cardoso, 2022).

However, the policy landscape is not straightforward. Different forms of IP protect different subject matter. Trademarks may protect signs and brands; design rights may protect the appearance of products; copyright may protect original artistic expression; patents may protect technical inventions; and geographical indications may protect names linked to a specific place and production tradition. In practice, many creative and craft-based products combine several of these features at once. This creates both opportunities and legal complexity (Kohli, 2023; Covarrubia, 2019).

Several policy tensions arise in this context. One concerns the balance between protection and access. IP rights can incentivize investment, preserve quality, and support fair competition, but they may also be costly and difficult to navigate, especially for small and micro-enterprises. A second tension concerns innovation and tradition. Some frameworks are designed to reward individual novelty and originality, while others, such as geographical indications, may better reflect collective heritage, traditional knowledge, and regional production practices. A third tension concerns market integration and territorial identity. EU policy seeks to strengthen the internal market while also recognizing the economic and cultural value of local distinctiveness. A fourth tension concerns legal certainty and sectoral fit: rules developed with industrial production or conventional innovation models in mind do not always map neatly onto the realities of craft and applied art.

These issues have become particularly salient in the European Union. Recent developments, including the introduction of EU protection for geographical indications for craft and industrial products, reflect a broader recognition that existing IP frameworks do not always adequately capture the value embedded in non-agricultural regional products. More broadly, ongoing case law and legislative developments continue to test the boundaries between aesthetic creation, technical function, branding, and heritage protection (Zappalaglio, 2023; Kohli, 2023).

The central question is, therefore, not whether IP matters in this field, but how IP frameworks can be designed and applied so that they support creativity, innovation, cultural heritage, and regional development in a balanced and accessible way. Because the feasibility of IP protection often depends on resources, market exposure, and enforcement capacity, the toolkit includes the HEPHAESTUS IP Booklet (Appendix A) as a practical companion resource, supporting craft makers in navigating legal options (e.g., trademarks, design rights, copyright, patents, and geographical indications) and in making proportionate choices that strengthen long-term sustainability without overburdening small enterprises. The IP HEPHAESTUS booklet will also be introduced at the annual symposium in Bassano del Grappa, in April 2026. Additionally, it is part of Task 4.2 and D4.2, the life-long learning methodology and will be tested and applied throughout the final year of the project.

9.0 Concluding Remarks

This report has provided an empirically grounded and analytically informed account of sustainable business models in the craft sector across the HEPHAESTUS ecosystems. The findings demonstrate that craft-based enterprises operate through configurations in which economic viability is closely intertwined with cultural heritage, ecological responsibility, social relations, and place-based embeddedness. As such, conventional business model frameworks, while useful as a shared descriptive vocabulary, require a more flexible and reflective application to adequately capture the complexity of value creation in craft contexts.

Across the cases, a consistent pattern emerges in which value is multi-dimensional and often condensed within products, services, and shared experiences. This challenges revenue-centered approaches and highlights the need to account for multiple, co-existing forms of value. The analytical prisms developed in the report – such as negotiating time, making place, forming responsiveness, and balancing growth with limits – provide a structured way of identifying and articulating these recurring tensions. They also illustrate that sustainability in craft is achieved through maintaining the conditions that enable practices to remain coherent, resilient, and meaningful over time (Luckman, 2015; Friedman et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the report emphasizes the importance of the relationship between the craft value proposition and the hoped-for customer. In many cases, value realization depends on forms of engagement that go beyond transactional exchange, involving processes of learning, participation, and responsiveness. This points to a broader, socially formative role of craft, where business practices contribute to shaping how value is understood and appreciated by customers and publics.

The resulting toolkit translates these insights into a set of practical orientations that can support craft makers in reflecting on their own business models and exploring context-specific pathways. In this sense, the report contributes not only to academic understanding, but also to the development of actionable knowledge aligned with the objectives of the HEPHAESTUS project and the broader European policy agenda on sustainable and culturally-grounded innovation.

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Appendix A - Intellectual Property Booklet

Funded by
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EU Intellectual Property Guide

for Artists, Craftmakers & Designers

ΗΣΡΗΑΕΣΤΥΣ

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Created by
Vishv Priya Kohli
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**Creative work is valuable,
but without protection it can be
copied, misused, or exploited
by others.**

**Intellectual Property (IP) gives
artists, craftmakers, and designers
legal tools to safeguard their work,
reputation, and income.**

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Types of IP

Trademark

+

Designs

for visual appearance
and brand identity
such as for a fashion
label

Copyright

for creative works
such as for paintings

Geographical Indication

for products tied to
place and tradition
such as for craft from
a specific region

Patent

for technical
inventions such as for
innovative materials
or processes

Trademark

What it protects

Words, logos, colors, sounds, packaging that distinguish goods/services

Duration

10 years, renewable indefinitely

Why it matters

- Builds brand recognition and customer loyalty
- Prevents competitors from using confusingly similar signs

Tips

Search the EUIPO database before choosing a brand name

Example

Hauck v Stokke on 3D chair protection – see next page for full case

Legal basis

Regulation (EU) 2017/1001 on the EU Trade Mark

Trademark Case

Hauck v Stokke, the “Tripp Trapp” chair

Story

Stokke tried to protect the 3D shape of its iconic children’s chair as a trade mark. A competitor sold similar chairs and argued the “chair-shape-as-a-mark” should never have been registered, because the shape is too tied to what the product is and why people buy it.

Key lesson

Trade marks are for brand origin, not for locking up product shapes that are essential to the product’s nature, needed for its function, or that give the product substantial value.

What it means for you

If your craft product’s look is the selling point, don’t bet everything on trade mark protection. Use a trade mark for the name/logo, and consider design protection (for appearance) or copyright (if original), and patent (if technical). Keep brand cues separate from “the product’s best-looking bits.”

Now, have you considered ... ?

- Picking a sign that’s distinctive, not just descriptive (“Handmade Copenhagen” is... legally sleepy)
- Doing a clearance search (names/logos/nearby spellings)
- Choosing the right Nice classes for your goods/services (45-class system)
- Using your mark consistently (same spelling, same look)
- Putting basic brand rules in writing (license terms for stockists/collabs)

Designs

What it protects

The appearance of a product: lines, contours, shapes, textures, ornamentation, and color

Duration

3 years for unregistered designs and 25 years (5x5) for registered designs – these are protected for 5 years at a time and can be renewed 5 times

Why it matters

Protects the look of your products, not their function

Tips

Register before showing your design at fairs/exhibitions

Example

DOCERAM v CeramTec on welding pins – see next page for full case

Legal basis

Regulation (EU) 2024/2822

Designs Case

DOCERAM v CeramTec, on welding pins

Story

DOCERAM had registered Community designs for small industrial components. CeramTec attacked the designs, saying their shapes were chosen only because they work that way, not because they look that way.

Key lesson

A design won't protect features of appearance solely dictated by technical function. It's not enough to say "other shapes could also work". You must show that non-technical choices (visual/shape decisions) played a real role.

What it means for you

If you want design protection for (say) a clasp, handle, hinge, nozzle, loom-part, or tool component: document your aesthetic choices. Save sketches, prototypes, mood boards, and "why we chose this curve/ratio/edge". That paper trail helps prove your form wasn't just function in a trench coat.

Now, have you considered ... ?

- Documenting the design with clean images (views/angles) suitable for filing
- Filing early if you want stronger certainty (registration)
- For collections/variants, mapping what's a "family" vs separate filings
- Tracking competitors and keeping screenshots of suspected copying

Copyright

What it protects

Original artistic works: paintings, photographs, sculptures, crafts, music, digital art, literature, films, software

Duration

Life of the author
+70 years

Why it matters

Control reproduction, distribution, public performance, communication, and adaptations

Tips

- Always sign and date your work
- Keep drafts or sketches as proof of authorship
- Consider 'Creative Commons' if you want to allow sharing under conditions

Example

Cofemel v G-Star Raw on clothing designs – see next page for full case

Legal basis

- Directive 2001/29/EC (InfoSoc Directive)
- Directive (EU) 2019/790 (Digital Single Market Directive)

Copyright Case

Cofemel v G-Star Raw, on clothing designs

Story

A dispute over whether clothing designs (jeans and tops) could get copyright protection. Some national approaches tried to demand extra hurdles like “artistic value”. The CJEU pulled the brakes on that.

Key lesson

In EU law, copyright hinges on originality (the author’s own intellectual creation). No extra “beauty test” is allowed. Applied art, fashion, patterns, and product aesthetics can be protected if they’re original.

What it means for you

For textiles, prints, ceramic motifs, graphics, and decorative forms: keep evidence of creative choices (drafts, iterations, files with timestamps). If your work is original, copyright may arise automatically, and it can complement design rights instead of replacing them.

Now, have you considered ... ?

- Saving process proof: drafts, pattern development, toolpaths, moodboards, “why this choice” notes
- Contracts: clarifying who owns what with photographers, freelancers, collaborators
- Using clear licensing terms for customers (what they can do with your pattern/prints)

Geographical Indication

(GI)

What it protects

- Products whose quality, reputation, or characteristics are linked to their geographical origin
- Applies to craft and industrial products since Regulation (EU) 2023/2411

Duration

Unlimited, as long as the product maintains its reputation and link to the region

Why it matters

- Protects traditional knowledge and community reputation
- Prevents misuse (e.g., cheap imitations)

Tips

Join local associations to apply for GI recognition collectively

Example

Queso Manchego on evocation via imagery – see next page for full case

Legal basis

Regulation (EU) 2023/2411

GI Case

Queso Manchego, on evocation via imagery

Story

A producer used imagery and signs associated with “La Mancha” (think: the region’s cultural cues) on cheeses that were not PDO “Queso Manchego”. The question: can you “evoke” a protected name without using the name? Yes.

Key lesson

GI/PDO protection can be triggered by figurative elements (images, symbols, visual storytelling), not just words. The overall effect on the average consumer matters.

What it means for you

For ceramics and textiles (especially with the new craft/industrial GI direction in the EU), treat place-linked cues as high-voltage: names, maps, flags, iconic landscapes, traditional costumes, famous local motifs. Even if you don’t write “Made in X”, your label design might still “whisper X” loudly enough to cause trouble. Before leaning on regional vibes, check whether that place-name is protected as a GI/PDO/PGI and design accordingly.

Now, have you considered ... ?

- Checking the geographical link: qualities/reputation attributable to place + local know-how
- Organising as a producer group (often essential in practice)
- Drafting product specification: materials, method, boundaries, control plan
- Planning enforcement: monitoring marketplaces and misuse-by-evocation risks

Patent

What it protects

Technical inventions that are new, inventive, and industrially applicable

Duration

Up to 20 years

Why it matters

- Protects innovative processes or materials
- Less relevant for pure art/design but valuable for craft techniques

Tips

- Seek professional help before filing, patents are complex
- Never disclose before filing: novelty is essential

Example

Centrafarm v Sterling Drug on patent exhaustion & parallel trade – see next page for full case

Legal basis

Regulation (EU) No 1257/2012 + European Patent Convention (EPC)

Patent Case

Centrafarm v Sterling Drug, on patent exhaustion & parallel trade

Story

A patented product was lawfully placed on the market in one Member State by the patentee (or with consent). A third party then moved it across borders and sold it in another Member State. The patentee tried to use the patent to stop that resale.

Key lesson

Once you (or someone with your consent) put a patented product on the EU internal market, patent rights can't be used to block intra-EU resale of those same goods. That clashes with free movement of goods.

What it means for you

If you patent a product (a tool, a mechanism, a functional craft innovation), your patent is great for stopping unauthorised making and first-time selling. But it's not a magic wand for controlling every downstream resale across the EU/EEA. Plan your distribution with contracts, pricing strategy, and brand differentiation, not just enforcement dreams.

Now, have you considered ... ?

- Not disclosing before filing (or get professional advice first)
- Define the invention: what's new, what problem it solves, what makes it non-obvious
- Budget reality check: filing, prosecution, translations, renewals
- Do a freedom-to-operate scan if you're commercialising a new mechanism/material/process

What are you protecting?

Trademark

brand / sign
(name · logo ·
label look)

Designs

product
appearance
(shape · pattern ·
ornamentation)

Copyright

creative
expression
(drawings ·
patterns · artworks)

**Geographical
Indication**

place-linked
reputation /
producers
know-how

Patent

technical invention
(how it works /
how it is made)

Avoid self sabotage

if design or patent
might matter, consider filing
before public disclosure

Remember evidence of...

dated records such as
sketches, prototypes,
invoices, workshop logs,
photos, and version history

EU Support & Resources

Trademark

&

Designs

reach out to EUIPO -
the European Union
Intellectual Property
Office

Patent

reach out to
EPO - European
Patent Office

**Geographical
Indication**

reach out to European
Commission GI Portal

Copyright

and for else, reach out
to National IP offices
and/or to local
craft/trade associations

Find all resources you need here:
<https://www.euipo.europa.eu/en>

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Appendix B

Student Presentations - BOFA Challenge

1. Birdholm
2. The Circular Days - Reimagining the Bornholm Craft Weeks
3. The Kiln Innovation Hub
4. Re:form
5. Demeter

Birdholm

Slow Tourism:

How can the public sector support slow tourism initiatives, such as the immersive experiences, to position circular crafts as a driver of cultural tourism and socio-economic resilience?

The problem

- Seasonal Tourists*
- Dependence on summer season*
- Local economy suffering under it*
- increased littering*
- Disturbance to wildlife*

Birdwatchers as sustainable Tourists

- Willing to pay more
- Nature enthusiasts
- Sustainable mindset
- Mostly travel by foot
- Used to also travel in offseasons

Why Bornholm?

- Rare Bird Species
- Important Migration Stop
- Well-Developed Birdwatching Infrastructure
- Affordable Compared to Other Birding Hotspots

Our Solution

Circular Craftsmanship as the Foundation of Sustainable Birding Tourism

Birding infrastructure

- High-quality observation points, made from repurposed materials.

Glamping experiences

- Unique accommodations make Birdholm a multi-day experience.

Crafting and workshops

- Visitors participate in workshops, crafting birdhouses and taking waste home.

Impact

How BOFA Can Leverage
Circular Craftsmanship for
Cultural & Economic Resilience

Slow Tourism as a Growth Strategy

- Off season appeal (April and October)
- Encourages longer stays, deeper engagement, and sustainable visitor flow.
- Moves beyond traditional tourism models by integrating hands-on, immersive experiences.

Circular Crafts as a Socio-Economic Driver

- Creates jobs, preserves traditions, and builds community pride.
- Economically sustainable: Revenue from birdwatchers covers key costs such as teacher salaries and infrastructure maintenance.

Partners

BirdLife International

- Bird guide training programs based on international standards.
- Certification for local guides to improve their expertise & credibility.
- Access to global birdwatching networks for visitor outreach.

Scandinavian Airlines (SAS) & Bornholm Airport

- Special eco-travel discounts for birdwatchers flying to Bornholm.
- In-flight videos & magazines promoting Bornholm as a must-visit birding destination.
- Collaboration on birdwatching-themed travel packages

Danish Ornithological Society (DOF – Dansk Ornitologisk Forening)

- Local guide education, species identification courses.
- Certification of Bornholm as a "Top Birdwatching Site" in Denmark.
- Scientific collaboration to create seasonal bird migration reports.

The Circular Days - Reimagine the Bornholm Craft Weeks

Art of Innovation – Mar 2025

SLOW TOURISM

- **Meaningful experiences & rediscovering local culture ⇒ high-quality travel experience.**
- **Tackles challenges of modern life: stress, time pressure & lack of human connection.**
- **An alternative to mass tourism, encouraging immersive and mindful travel.**

PROBLEM

TOURISTS MUST BE PART OF THE **SOLUTION** BY ACTIVELY ENGAGING IN SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES

Regenerative

Immersion

Co-creation

Community

BORNHOLM
CRAFTWEEKS

SOLUTION

INCLUDE **CIRCULARITY** PRINCIPLES INTO THE CRAFT WEEKS BY BRINGING BOFA'S QUALITIES

**Design for
longevity**

Recycle

**Collaborative
economy**

PRODUCT

Brining **circularity** and **slow tourism** to Bornholms Craft Weeks

Circularity Days

Four days **add-on** to existing week in Bornholm

Day 1 - Sustainability/circularity workshop day with Bofa

Day 2-3 - Use of artistic waste materials in Workshops to create new art

Day 4 - Final exhibition of artworks in existing spaces over the island

Circularity Passport

- Collecting stamps of workshop participation
- Making their experience collectable & tangible
- Incentivise tourist to come back every year

IMPACT: CREATING LASTING VALUE

INVOLVING LOCAL COMMUNITIES, DISCOVERING HERITAGE & FOCUSING ON SUSTAINABILITY

01

Involve local communities:

By offering free passports to island's residents

02

Discovering the heritage - making tourists stay longer:

By transforming the Craft Weeks into a 2 week event

03

Increase tourist's connection with the local craft & community:

By initiating people to return to the festival every year with the 3-year passport

04

Having an ecological and ethical vision:

By raising awareness on sustainability with additional trainings

LINKING GROUP WORK TO COURSE

INVOLVING LOCAL COMMUNITIES, DISCOVERING HERITAGE & FOCUSING ON SUSTAINABILITY

01

Context-Driven Innovation

Viewed through ethnographic experience lens and local cultural context to find challenges

02

Incremental & Community-Driven Change

Small, sustainable improvements can have a lasting impact, aligning with local ecosystems and slow innovation

03

Public Involvement & Ownership

Engaging tourists and locals as co-creators rather than passive consumers fosters responsible innovation

04

Network Model of Innovation

Innovation is increasingly dependent on interconnected ecosystems rather than isolated efforts

WHERE DOES BOFA COME IN?

BOFA STANDS FOR CIRCULARITY - LET'S BRING IT TO THE CRAFT WEEKS!

BOFA

- Collects & prepare materials for artistic reuse
- Logistics for safe material storage & distribution
- Supports sustainability workshops
- The circularity leader of the event

HEPHAESTUS

- Facilitates new technology integration into circular crafts
- Translate living lab methodology to visitors and artists
- Bridges research with artistic experimentation.

CHALLENGES

RESHAPING TRADITION WHILE **MAINTAINING QUALITY**

01

GETTING EVERYONE ON BOARD

- Convincing organizers and artists to embrace change
- Need for clear communication and a strong vision to show the benefits of this new approach.

02

LOGISTICS & ART PRESERVATION

- Transporting, storing, and maintaining artwork & art waste for future editions
- Need of a system to ensure that art remains safe and reusable
- BOFA's support in handling logistics and preservation

THANK YOU

BOFA x CBS

THE KILN Innovation Hub

March 2025

How can public sector organisations like BOFA foster circular business models within arts and crafts by facilitating innovation within recycling of sanitation and waste material?

Bornholm is pursuing the ambitious goal of becoming Europe's first Zero Waste island by 2032

- **Frontrunner** in circular Economy
- **Zero waste** island by 2032
- BOFA as **central manager & driver** of circular initiatives across the island (Recycling, Arts & Crafts etc.)

- Broad range of circular **initiatives** which seem to be **loosely connected**
- Fragmented projects increase the **communication efforts** and hinders scaling
- **Dependency** on external funding

*"How can Bornholm **unlock the full potential** of circular innovation and scale its Zero Waste ambitions?"*

Answer

Circular Innovation Hub

- Centralisation
- Entrepreneurship
- Knowledge Exchange

Institutionalising Innovation

- Connect interdisciplinary stakeholders
- Allow circular business models to scale

BOFA and Bornholm drive multiple initiatives to reach being waste free...

*There is no **central platform** to promote **co-creation, knowledge exchange** and the development of **new sustainable businesses** between the waste management industry, the skilled trades, research and tourism.*

...However, there are obstacles that must be overcome by

There is no central platform to promote co-creation, knowledge exchange and the development of new sustainable businesses between the waste management industry, the skilled trades, research and tourism.

Hypotheses

H1

Lack of **centralisation** reduces efficiency, creates confusion, and leads to a poor overview of all initiatives.

H2

Co-creation primarily takes place on a small scale, which may limit its potential for maximising impact.

H3

Knowledge exchange predominantly happens in silos which limits knowledge spillover.

H4

Bornholm needs to **institutionalise** innovation to ensure scalability and longevity.

Literature

Florida (2003) says bringing talent together makes things easier, spreads ideas, and attracts skilled people because location still matters.

Ledingham et al. (2024) says that sustainable innovation needs collaboration across sectors and cannot be driven top-down.

Ledingham et al. (2024) argues that collective intelligence improves problem-solving by bringing together diverse data, ideas, and insights

Vinsel (2017) argues for focusing on expertise over trendy fads, while **Forbes (2018)** highlights the need to embed innovation into industry norms

Key Takeaways

- ✓ Establishing a centralised hub for accessibility
- ✓ Scaling impactful co-creation through collaborative, interdisciplinary initiative
- ✓ Creating a knowledge exchange nexus to facilitate continuous learning
- ✓ Building sustainable infrastructure for longevity instead of relying on temporary projects

A solution that brings together...

Key Takeaways

- ✓ Establishing a **centralised hub** for accessibility
- ✓ Scaling impactful **co-creation** through collaborative, interdisciplinary initiative
- ✓ Creating a **knowledge exchange** nexus to facilitate continuous learning
- ✓ Building **sustainable infrastructure** for longevity instead of relying on temporary projects

Infrastructure

- ✓ One-stop-shop and Nexus
- ✓ Knowledge Portal

Entrepreneurship

- ✓ Maker Space with tools to share
- ✓ Incubation & Entrepreneurship programme

Knowledge

- ✓ Open Workshops for everybody
- ✓ Advisory & Mentoring by Partners

Events

- ✓ Keynotes & Panels from business and academia
- ✓ Networking Events bridging professionals
- ✓ Social Space to spend leisure time

Solution - Proof of Concept and CSFs

CIRCULAR INNOVATION HUB

A platform driving **circular economy solutions** in Africa.

- **Accelerator Programm:** Supports startups from idea to scale.
- **Advisory Services:** Guides businesses on circular strategies.
- **Co-working Space & Events:** Provides space for collaboration.
- **Corporate Training:** Equips companies for sustainable transitions.

Islands of Innovation
Interreg Europe

European Union
European Regional
Development Fund

A project transforming European islands into **innovation test-beds** to diversify economies and retain talent.

- **Isolation situation** can trigger innovations & provide a distinct, resourceful environment.
- **Self Reliance** and Strong **Community Involvements.**
- Strengthening **Research** and **Innovation**
- Promoting **Business Investment** in R&I.

Copenhagen Fablab

An open-access, **user-driven workshop** in Copenhagen for experimenting with digital fabrication and prototyping

- **Facilities:** Provides tools for wood, metal, textile, and digital fabrication.
- **Access:** Free to use without membership; adhere to community guidelines.
- **Philosophy:** Emphasizes knowledge sharing and collaborative learning.

Locational Factors

Sustainable Business Acceleration

Knowledge Sharing

From Vision to Reality – Phased Roll-Out of THE KILN to Drive Lasting Change

In order to **successfully reach**
their **ambitions...**

...BOFA should **invest**
into **THE KILN...**

...to **unlock full potential** of
current and future **initiatives.**

Thank you!

Nina
Madsen

Marc
Stäglich

Felix
Schraff

Raphael
Sauer

Nicolas
Vassalli

BOFA

Art of Innovation presentation

by

Catja Jensen, Laura Due & Tobias Glesner

Research Question and Solution

Question: How can public sector organizations like BOFA foster circular business models within arts and crafts by facilitating innovation within recycling of sanitation and waste material (including discarded toilets, sinks, etc.)?

Solution: RE:FORM STUDIOS X BOFA

- **Mosaic-style sustainable public benches, water fountains, bicycle stations, and outdoor showers made from recycled sanitary materials**

The Visual

Why and Where?

- Based on the *Development Plan for Tourism on Bornholm towards 2030*
 - **Tourism plan:** In 2030, Bornholm is a year-round, sustainable, and preferred travel destination with high quality and international impact

Primary locations

- The plan focuses on 3 geographical areas: **Aakirkeby, Nexø, and Hasle.**
 - Selected as they hold new and untapped potential
- Focus on small-town communities such as **Snogebæk, Vestermarie, and Årsballe**

Additional locations

- Urban Centers: Svaneke, Rønne, Gudhjem, Allinge
- Nature Areas: Almindingen Forest, Dueodde Beach
- Cycling Routes: Rønne-Nexø Path, Hammershus Trail

Benefits of Using Recycled Ceramics for Public Benches

Environmental Benefits

Reduces landfill waste by **upcycling broken toilets, sinks, and tiles.**

Lowers **CO₂ emissions** by minimizing the need for new materials.

Supports **BOFA's circular economy goals** and strengthens Bornholm's sustainability reputation.

Economic Benefits

Low-cost alternative to **imported stone or concrete benches.**

Creates **local business opportunities** for artisans and designers.

Boosts **eco-tourism** by adding unique, sustainable public art and seating.

Cultural & Social Benefits

Engages **local artists** in designing benches, fostering community involvement.

Makes public spaces **more visually appealing and unique to Bornholm.**

Reinforces Bornholm's **commitment to sustainability and creative reuse.**

Implementation & Stakeholder Collaboration

Partner with BOFA to collect discarded toilets, sinks, and tiles.

**BOFA (Bornholm's Waste Management) will provide waste logistics, sorting, and material processing.*

Engage local artisans and designers to create mosaic benches and sculptural seating.

**ACAB (Arts & Crafts Association Bornholm) will involve local artists for unique designs and exhibitions.*

**Royal Danish Academy (KGLA) will contribute architectural expertise and sustainable design research.*

Select key locations in towns, nature spots, and cycling routes.

**Bornholm's Regional Municipality (BRK) will approve and facilitate installations in public spaces.*

**Center for Tourism & Research (CRT) will help integrate locations into tourism and sustainability initiatives.*

Pilot the project with a few benches in Rønne or Svaneke.

**RE:FORM STUDIOS will support circular economy models and community engagement strategies.*

BOFA

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Appendix C - Toolkit for business models for sustainable craft

SOCIETAL COSTS